

Equality Commission

FOR NORTHERN IRELAND

ANNUAL REPORT 2001 - 2002

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Equality Commission for Northern Ireland
Equality House
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THE COMMISSION'S MISSION STATEMENT

To value and promote respect for diversity, eliminate unlawful discrimination and achieve equality of opportunity for all.

Equality Commission for Northern Ireland

Presented to the Northern Ireland Assembly in accordance with paragraph 7 (4) of schedule 8 to the Northern Ireland Act 1998

A copy of this report will be laid before each House of Parliament in accordance with paragraphs 5 (3) and (4) of schedule 8 to the Northern Ireland Act 1998.

Equality Commission for Northern Ireland

Mr Des Browne
Parliamentary Under Secretary of State
Castle Buildings
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Dear Minister

I have pleasure in submitting to you the third annual report of the Equality Commission for Northern Ireland, covering the period 1 April 2001 to 31 March 2002.

Commissioners and staff have worked together with enthusiasm and commitment to fulfil the Commission's statutory remit, and to promote ownership of equality and fairness in our society. I am grateful to them all.

On behalf of the Commission, I would like to express our appreciation of the assistance given to the Commission by officials of the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister, and of the Northern Ireland Office.

Yours sincerely

JOAN HARBISON
Chief Commissioner

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Chief Commissioner's Foreword

During this year we have seen increasing evidence of the way in which thinking about equality is changing and I believe a greater engagement with the issues of inequality. The many people, representative of all our stakeholder groups, who joined with us to celebrate our move to our new premises, demonstrated commitment to and support for creating a culture of equality throughout our society. It was a most encouraging and exciting day and was followed by a successful conference which confronted the issues of what equality means and how far we have achieved a society in which everyone has a stake and an opportunity to contribute.

In our discussions with Ministers and MLAs, both individually and at party level, and in providing evidence to Assembly Committees, we have found an increasing willingness to discuss the whole spectrum of equality and to see it as something which affects all our lives. The consultation and dialogue we have been involved in have produced some real and dynamic debates about important issues which people feel deeply about and hold strong opinions on. This we believe can only help to raise awareness of the inequalities in our society and a deeper understanding of the many issues involved. I believe this higher level of discourse is evidence of our role in building the equality culture which is our core corporate objective.

Building partnerships involves getting out and about, and we are grateful to Derry City Council and Newtownabbey Borough Council for welcoming us to their offices, and joining us at the receptions we held to meet members of a wide range of local groups. Commissioners visited other parts of Northern Ireland when they chaired the consultation seminars on single equality legislation and the "Louder than Words" roadshows on the Disability Discrimination Act.

Deputy Chief Commissioner Bronagh Hinds, as chair of the Statutory Duty Committee, has played an important role in developing partnerships with and between public bodies and the voluntary and community sector on the implementation of Section 75 of the Northern Ireland Act. We have achieved challenging objectives in work on the statutory duty this year, especially around the approval of equality schemes

Our involvement with the Chairs/Chief Commissioners and Chief Executives of related organisations in Great Britain and Ireland through the Joint Equality and Human Rights Forum has proved to be a mutually supportive and productive relationship, as has our involvement in Europe through the Advisory Committee on Equal Opportunities between Women and Men. At an international level, other mutually beneficial contacts have been made with politicians, policy-makers and equality agencies in several countries.

It has been an exciting, busy and useful year.

Chief Executive's Introduction

The report describes in detail the effectiveness of our work in our second full year of existence. Its structure follows the broad strategic objectives of our 2000 - 2003 corporate plan and the more detailed objectives, performance indicators and targets of the annual operational plan. As will be seen from the text which follows, we set out at the beginning of the year under review with 14 objectives and 33 associated targets. Progress with meeting these targets is set out in the report - overall, we met 25 of the 33 (76%) and partly met the target in 4 (12%) instances. For a further four targets (12%), the work was deferred, in three instances because of changes to the timetable for legislative change and in the fourth because of ongoing integration work internally.

Achievements this year included raising awareness of the Commission by 5% since the year 2000; holding our first Annual Conference on equality, mapping the equality agenda in Northern Ireland, with high rates of overall satisfaction by participants (94%); contributing to the development of public policy through commenting on consultations in key areas; extending and clarifying the law in key areas of employers' duties, political opinion, and access to justice; effecting change with employers and service providers through litigation; promoting good practice with employers and service providers through a range of means, with an increasing focus on delivery of services in an integrated way; ensuring high levels of compliance with Fair Employment and Treatment Order monitoring provisions; and promoting reasonable adjustments among employers and service providers through a successful targeted campaign attracting over 800 participants in events across Northern Ireland. Much of our work is achieved through partnerships with others and this too is recorded in our Annual Report.

Particular highlights this year included considerable progress with the approval of public authorities' Equality Schemes, with the majority now approved and public authorities making progress with screening exercises and equality impact assessments through the year under review. We organised six workshops on EQIAs, which proved most successful in increasing skills and knowledge of dealing with the processes.

My introduction would be incomplete without reference to the work we undertook to develop our ideas for single equality legislation. We published two detailed analyses of the key issues as well as responding to OFMDFM's consultation and engaging widely with stakeholders across the sectors in developing our thinking. The development of the Single Equality Act is a great opportunity for Northern Ireland to do something very special and very forward-looking, taking account of the changing and deepening understanding of what equality can mean to a society. We have set ourselves the objective of doing all we can to promote just such legislation, drawing on the Commission's unique body of experience in working with equality law, and working with those who are affected by it as employers and employees, service providers and service users.

Vital too in this introduction is reference to the move in August 2001 to Equality House from the three sites we had been using up to then; this represented a significant milestone for the organisation. This move was done on time and with minimum disruption to our services. The high quality of our new offices, not least in their accessibility to

disabled people, and simply the fact of our all being together at last, was a huge step forward. I found the opening ceremony positive and inspiring, and I have been glad to welcome very many visitors to meetings, seminars and training sessions in Equality House since then.

The challenge and achievement has been to take forward, indeed to lead, an integrated and coherent equality agenda while keeping a focus on the individual concerns which go to make up that agenda.

We continued through the year to monitor progress against our objectives and the allocation of resources to the various aspects of our work - this is set out in the Financial Statement included in this report. As you will see, the Comptroller and Auditor General has qualified his opinion on our accounts for the period, in relation to the identification of liabilities for legal fees. The Commission is working to address the matters raised in the coming year.

Particular pressure became evident in respect of expenditure on legal fees towards the end of the year and steps were taken to address this, including bringing forward a review of the legal assistance strategy under which the Commission exercises its discretion to assist applicants with their complaints. This work will also continue into the coming year.

I look forward to another year of constructive work for equality in Northern Ireland.

STRATEGIC PRIORITY ONE:

Mainstreaming equality and promoting social inclusion

Objective: To raise awareness of equality issues

Performance Indicator: Increase in awareness

Target: To have analysed baseline data and set targets for increases

Result: Target met

The Commission engaged in several high profile and successful activities to increase public awareness of equality issues.

We assessed levels of awareness on equality issues through a public attitudes survey. This asked about people's knowledge of the equality legislation and the Commission, and their support for anti-discrimination laws. The results show that the public have a good grasp of the groups covered by existing anti-discrimination laws (for example, 75% knew that people were protected from discrimination on the grounds of religious belief and political opinion) and of the role of the Commission (for example, 66% recognised that the Commission has a role in "ensuring fairness in the job market" and 65% in "acting against discrimination") and that there is support for extending the law to cover sexual orientation and age. The survey showed that we have already achieved our 2000 - 2003 corporate plan's 5% target for increasing public awareness of the Commission, compared to a similar survey carried out in 2000. We however decided to set a new target, an extra 5% increase in 2002 - 2003.

We held the first annual equality conference on key issues for the equality agenda. Topics included the law, Europe, government and civil society. The event was extremely well attended, with over 250 participants. Feedback was extremely positive, with 94% of evaluation forms recording "very good" or "good" for overall satisfaction. We achieved our goal of raising awareness of the current state of the equality agenda in Northern Ireland and bringing together stakeholders with a range of priorities and interests.

We contribute to raising awareness through all our work including publishing research and tribunal decisions, organising equality events, and working with many interested groups and individuals. A successful advertising campaign, starting just before the end of the year but designed and planned in the previous period, was also part of this process. It highlighted the Commission's services for black and minority ethnic people and for people with disabilities.

We continued to monitor media reporting on minority ethnic issues and challenged any inaccurate or stereotyped reporting, particularly on Travellers. Examples included our rebuttal in the local press of unjustified denigration of the Irish Traveller community by

some local representatives when a controversy arose about proposed Travellers' sites in County Down, and our defence on radio of the right of Travellers to legal protection against discrimination.

Research is important in raising awareness and throughout this report there are summaries of some of the research undertaken across the equality agenda throughout the year. We published, jointly with the Equality Authority, "Charting the equality agenda: a coherent framework for equality strategies in Ireland North and South" by Katherine Zappone. It reflects the broad scope of the equality agenda, and clarifies key principles; the rationale and value of such an agenda, the political barriers, and the application of equality strategies to areas of employment, service provision and policy-making. To build on and utilise the report, the Joint Equality and Human Rights Forum agreed to do more work on the implications of the strategies for multiple identity, and this will be carried out next year.

In spite of significant improvements in women's experience of the labour market, there are still stereotyped views of "men's work" and "women's work", and these stereotypes, all too often reflected in lower pay and status, can be fixed at an early stage. Research into children's views on men's and women's work was published as "Betty the builder - Neil the nurse" and launched at a seminar at Queen's University. It showed that although children saw most jobs as appropriate for both sexes, they identified a third of occupations as for one sex only. Teachers do feel responsible for challenging gender stereotypes, but other issues seem to take priority in practice. To help them incorporate this into their work, we are currently supporting research on equality awareness in teacher education and training.

Objective: To help marginalised groups to challenge inequality

Performance Indicator: Increase in capacity

Target: To have delivered and evaluated a capacity building programme

Result: Target met

The Commission is helping marginalised groups to challenge inequalities through a number of different means.

We commissioned research to identify the barriers which prevent people with disabilities accessing legal services. The final report will highlight potential disincentives to complainants and so contribute to increasing the accessibility of our own legal services.

Alongside this initiative, we developed a training project to inform people with disabilities of their rights, and to build their capacity to use this information effectively. Working in partnership with disability rights based organisations, we developed the training to include an introduction to the Disability Discrimination Act, an understanding of "reasonable adjustments", and how to exercise one's rights at different stages of the employment process. The training will be piloted and evaluated in the incoming year.

We are aware of the growing vulnerability of refugees and asylum seekers in Northern Ireland. To try to build their capacity in an integrated way, a Refugee and Asylum

Services Co-ordination Group, of which we are a member, has been set up on a Northern Ireland wide basis. The group also includes key agencies which represent, and offer services to, refugees and asylum seekers.

Objective: To promote better equality legislation

Performance Indicator: Impact on Government

Target: To have achieved Government support for Commission recommendations in the Single Equality Act and in early amendment to Race Relations (NI) Order 1997

Result: Target deferred, as result of change in timetable

The Northern Ireland Executive in its first Programme for Government gave a commitment to take forward work on a Single Equality Bill (SEB) and to introduce this to the Assembly in 2002. The Commission set out at the beginning of the year under review to influence Government thinking on the contents of the Bill and to see its recommendations taken up by Government. At the beginning of 2002, it was announced that there would be a change to the timetable for the introduction of the SEB. This would involve a lengthier process, with plans at that stage for the SEB going to the Assembly in autumn 2004, becoming law in 2005. As a result, while significant work was undertaken during the year under review, we have yet to see the actual influence it will have on Government, pending the publication of proposals. Meeting the target was thus not possible in the original timescale.

The Commission has unique experience in working with equality legislation and with the people who have challenged discrimination over the years. Our work on the proposed Bill has been designed to influence the adoption of our key recommendations in the new legislation, as well as by our statutory duty to keep the various pieces of equality legislation under review and to make recommendations for change to Government.

Our aim is to ensure legislation which harmonises to the highest standard, applies the best of existing equality legislation to all and complies with international equality and human rights standards. We are also aware of the need to look to developments in Europe, Ireland and the rest of the UK.

Staff and Commissioners worked intensively on our position on single equality legislation and on our response to the initial consultation by the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister. We submitted the questionnaire response to the OFMDFM consultation at the end of the summer, and also gave evidence to the Committee of the Centre.

Our response was followed, in October 2002, by a published position paper setting out our views on a number of areas and also seeking inputs on areas where the Commission had identified the need for further consideration. To further develop our thinking, we held one-to-one and roundtable meetings with interested groups, including the CBI, the Equality Coalition, the legal profession and academics. Six public seminars were held throughout Northern Ireland, chaired by Commissioners, to present the position paper and to gather the views of interested parties. The Commission met with OFMDFM in November to discuss our initial views and how best to engage and consult

throughout the course of the Bill. We held an intensive and productive conference - "Single equality legislation for a diverse community" - in Belfast in December 2001, with 125 participants.

In February 2002 we produced a further position paper and submitted this to OFMDFM. This considered good relations, definitions of discrimination, grounds of discrimination, exemptions and affirmative/positive action.

The Commission raised its concern at the intention to use regulations under the European Communities Act 1972 to bring in, in 2003, some of the requirements of the new European Race and Employment Equality Directives which stem from Article 13 of the Treaty of Amsterdam. This process will involve scrutiny by the Committee of the Centre, but not amendment by MLAs in the full Assembly. The original timetable for the Single Equality Bill would have enabled the changes required under the Directives to have been included in an overall review of the legislation, with full debate of the entire legislative programme in the Assembly, and the opportunity to go beyond the strict requirements of the Directives.

The Commission continued to measure progress on disability legislation against developments in Great Britain, to ensure parity for the people of Northern Ireland. We have been particularly active on the Special Educational Needs and Disability legislation for Northern Ireland. We expressed our disappointment that the legislation was being brought in more quickly in Great Britain, leaving disabled people in Northern Ireland at a considerable disadvantage. We also met with the Minister for Education (having met the Minister for Employment and Learning in the previous reporting year) and made recommendations on how the legislation could be improved here.

Objective: To ensure effective implementation of equality schemes

Performance Indicator: Evidence of effective implementation

Target: To have achieved effective implementation by at least 90% of public authorities

Result: Target met

The first annual progress report on the implementation of s75 duties during the period 2000-2001 has been completed. We are pleased with the progress reported - the overwhelming majority of schemes have been approved, screening exercises are well underway, we have provided effective training to public authorities, and they have undertaken meaningful work on mainstreaming equality in policy-making.

Through each public authority's report we have examined progress on implementation of the good relations duty. Work to date has included the development of strategies for delivering the good relations duty, or the inclusion of good relations objectives, performance indicators and targets in the plans of public authorities. The development of a Commission strategy for ensuring the effective implementation of the good relations duty is a key objective for us in the incoming year.

The first requirement for a public authority is to produce and consult on a draft equality scheme before submitting it to the Commission for approval. During the past year we approved 97% (113 of 117) of draft equality schemes. In the same period 60% (9 of 15)

of the public bodies designated by the Secretary of State in July 2000 have had their draft schemes approved. We continued to discuss with the other bodies the issues which need addressed in order that the schemes may be approved.

The second requirement is for each public body to screen its policies and draw up a timetable for carrying out equality impact assessments (EQIAs) on policies with significant equality implications. By the end of the year, of the 65 EQIAs which NI Departments were carrying out, 28 had reached stage 5 (decision-making) of the EQIA process.

To support this key method of mainstreaming equality, the Commission held six EQIA training workshops for the voluntary and community sector, trade unionists, s75 groups and public authorities, with appropriate training materials. Feedback from participants confirmed that the workshops met a strongly identified need to support them through this challenging new process of EQIAs and were highly successful in increasing their knowledge of and skills in working with the process - "a very useful course, much needed and timely" in the words of one participant. Ninety-eight percent of participants rated the workshops "excellent" or "good".

The Commission continues to provide this support and to build relationships with the bodies, groups and individuals most immediately affected by the s75 duties. The existing guidance on EQIA will be reviewed in the incoming year.

Objective: To build equality into policy making

Performance Indicator: Impact on Government and evidence of equality impacting on Government policy

Target: To have made detailed responses/recommendations on equality impact assessments and consultation documents in key areas

Result: Target met

The Commission responded to 12 EQIAs and 27 consultation papers this year - a full list of consultation responses is detailed in Appendix Seven. They cover especially health, education and employment.

As well as the obvious and key work on mainstreaming which the Commission carries out under section 75, we have targeted some areas on which to focus our attention.

The review of public procurement established by the Minister for Finance and Personnel provided a valuable opportunity for the Commission to raise the importance of using public sector purchasing power to pursue social strategies like equality and anti-discrimination. We supported the view in the consultation paper that the integration of public policy goals, including equality objectives, is an important means of mainstreaming.

The review of community relations provided scope for the Commission to highlight its role in promoting good relations and the importance of situating any debate about community relations policy in the context of equality legislation.

On a number of occasions through the year we sought to improve the opportunities for parents in the labour market, through our responses to policy initiatives on work and parents.

We also commented on the Executive's Second Programme for Government during the year under review. We highlighted the importance of ensuring that equality considerations were sufficiently mainstreamed within the priorities set out in the Programme, that individual actions must be sufficient to address the objectives and that the distribution of resources must reflect the need to promote equality of opportunity. Notably, the second Programme for Government devoted a chapter to consideration of the equality impact of the Programme, following discussions we had with OFMDFM and DFP officials on arrangements for the integration of the equality dimension into the Programme for Government. Discussions on developing this important process continued through the year.

In transport policy, we made recommendations on the issues particularly affecting people with disabilities, and women; issues of accessibility, frequency, and cost. The Commission has been active on the Key Stakeholder Group for the Belfast Metropolitan Area Transport Plan, in the review of the Transport for Disabled Persons Programme and in the Regional Transport Strategy.

To mainstream the needs of disabled people the Commission supported the establishment of a Promoting Social Inclusion Working Group on disability. This would give recognition to the fact that people with disabilities are routinely disadvantaged.

Mainstreaming the health needs of asylum seekers and refugees into policy making was highlighted through a conference organised jointly with the Department of Health, Social Services and Public Safety, other public sector agencies and NGOs.

The Commission continues to campaign for the needs of Irish Travellers to be mainstreamed into policy making. Unfortunately, Travellers remain one of Northern Ireland's most discriminated against and marginalised groups. We co-sponsored with the NI Housing Executive a conference, organised by the Traveller Movement (NI), on racial equality in the provision of Traveller accommodation.

Arising directly out of this initiative, the Commission in partnership with the Traveller Movement (NI) produced a consultative good practice guide to promote equality in planning for Travellers. This work addresses many of the issues raised by the Craigavon planning appeal of the previous year.

We hosted a roundtable on nomadism, which led to a submission on the inclusion of nomadism in the draft Bill of Rights.

The Working Families Tax Credit is designed to help the poorest households return to or stay in work. Research into WFTC showed considerable uncertainty about the different methods of payment and how to apply for them, and concerns about privacy, terms and conditions, and the effect on household budgeting.

STRATEGIC PRIORITY TWO: **Combating Discrimination and Promoting Equality**

Objective: To bring about change through enforcement

Performance Indicators: Changes in practices and procedures; complainant assistance provided to agreed standards; clarification/extension of the law

Targets: To have effected change in at least half of enforcement activities undertaken during 2001-2002; and to extend and clarify the law in identified areas

Result: Targets met

The Commission is committed to enforcing equality legislation effectively. We do this by giving information, guidance and, in some cases, financial assistance to people who believe they have been discriminated against. During the year we received 2681 legal enquiries. Of these, we assisted 661 people to pursue their case and 200 had assistance refused. All enquirers are given information and advice.

Of the people assisted by the Commission, 113 settled their cases. They received total compensation of over £1,157,000 from employers and service providers.

As can be seen from Appendix Three, 85 of 113 (75%) employers/service providers undertook to make changes in their policies or practices - shown in the remedial terms section of the tables. In the great majority of these cases, employers undertook to work with the Commission to tackle the problems raised by the case.

Some key decisions in cases which we assisted clarified and extended equality legislation on employers' duties, the meaning of political opinion, and access to justice.

Employers' duties: the successful case of Brannigan -v- Belfast City Council clarified employers' duties in relation to equal opportunity training and appropriate responses to sectarian harassment. The Fair Employment Tribunal considered that "reasonably practicable" methods of restraining harassment included electronic surveillance of access areas to places where incidents of sectarian graffiti had repeatedly occurred, comprehensive training of all employees concerned and the personal explanation to the workforce of the employer's policy on sectarian harassment once the incidents in question came to light.

A woman police officer was awarded over £20,000 for serious physical and verbal harassment in the case of Bradley -v- RUC. The tribunal noted that senior officers had failed to grasp the seriousness of the issue, and recommended a review of, and adequate training in, sexual harassment policies.

The year under review also saw the first tribunal decision under the Disability Discrimination Act in a case assisted by the Commission. In Winning -v- Belfast City Airport, the tribunal accepted that the employer had failed to make reasonable adjustments for the disabled applicant even in an industry in which safety considerations were paramount. In particular, the respondent had not undertaken a risk assessment or consulted with the applicant in order to establish whether it would be possible for him to continue in his original position.

Political opinion: the Court of Appeal dealt with the meaning of political opinion in Gill -v- NICEM, applying the ruling of the same Court in the 1994 case of McKay -v- Northern Ireland Public Service Alliance. This was that “political opinion” within the meaning of “religious belief and political opinion” in the fair employment legislation was not restricted to political opinion specific to Northern Ireland politics. However, the Court concluded that a policy of “anti-racism” as opposed to one of “cultural sensitivity” was not “an opinion relating to the policy of the government and matters touching upon the government of the state”.

Access to justice: in the case of Devlin -v- The United Kingdom, the European Court of Human Rights found that the issue by the Secretary of State of a Section 42 certificate breached Article 6 of the Convention, as it constituted a disproportionate restriction on the applicant’s right of access to a court. In doing so, the Court applied the earlier judgement in Tinnelly & McElduff -v- UK to a minor position in the civil service. The Court accepted that some civil service positions would involve “specific activities of the public service insofar as the latter is acting as the general depository of public authority responsible for protecting the general interests of the State or other public authorities” but concluded that the post for which the applicant had applied did not come within that category.

The Commission agreed a common enforcement policy on legal assistance in the first year of our corporate plan 2000 -2001, with a review to be carried out in 2002 - 2003. In the light of pressure on legal expenditure arising from an increase in cases assisted, we brought forward the review, which began as the year under review ended.

Objective: To raise awareness of advice and assistance

Performance Indicator: Increase in awareness

Target: To have collected and analysed baseline data/information and set targets for 2002-2003

Result: Target met

The survey described under Strategic Priority One showed that there are few differences between the various subgroups in their understanding of the role of the Commission: people over 65 were less likely to recognise the Commission’s role, as were those who were economically inactive and people with disabilities.

We are committed to informing people who feel that they may have been discriminated against about our advice and assistance services. This year alone we received nearly 10,000 enquiries from individuals, from employers and service providers, and others with an interest in equality matters. Almost a quarter of the enquiries were not tied to one particular form of discrimination; of the rest, the largest area of enquiry was disability discrimination (21%) closely followed by fair employment and treatment (19%). Most enquiries are employment-related (61%) with almost a third relating to recruitment and selection. Employers and service providers make up 38% of callers, while nearly half of all calls come from the general public.

Although most contact with the Commission is by telephone, contact through the website and e-mail has now surpassed enquiries by fax and letter. This year website and email contacts made up 11% of the total, and we have set ourselves the target of raising this

by 2-3% in the incoming year. We undertook a considerable programme of work to enlarge the website and make it more accessible.

We also increase awareness by including in all key publications an invitation to readers to use our information services; much of our work with the media is directed to letting people know their rights, as of course was the advertising campaign described earlier.

Objective: To promote good practice

Performance Indicators: Evaluation of user feedback; changes in practices and procedures

Targets: To have put in place integrated equality services for employers and service providers; to have achieved change in practices and procedures

Result: Targets met

Promoting good practice through training has always been a key part of the Commission's activity. This year we delivered 367 training sessions for employers, mainly on dealing with harassment, and recruitment and selection. Over 90% of training covered the full range of equality issues, disability, fair employment, gender and race, in an integrated way, with the rest focussing on specific areas. This work included 50 employer seminars held across Northern Ireland and attended by almost 1300 participants. Sixty per cent of our training was with private sector employers. The feedback from those attending training events is very positive, with over 95% of participants completing evaluation forms finding the sessions "of practical value" and demand for our services remains high. This is what we use as an indication that the participant organisation is likely to effect change in their practices and procedures.

Another advice initiative was our work with Invest NI and the Labour Relations Agency, on the production of an Employment Law & Good Practice Handbook. The handbook will be launched in April 2002.

The Commission has continued to respond to requests for advice from employers and service providers on the sensitive matter of flags and emblems. The decision in the judicial review on the Flags (Northern Ireland) Order 2000, which provided for the display of the Union Flag on designated buildings on designated days, has helped us develop our advice on the subject.

Target: To have developed a model integrated equality plan for employers

Result: Target partly met

Work began on drafting model integrated equality plans for employers. This will help employers create action plans to promote equality of opportunity in employment policies, practices and procedures. The draft will be consulted on, and a further draft will be piloted, in the incoming year.

We also produced a number of publications aimed at informing employers and services providers of their legal responsibilities, particularly in the area of disability. These and other Commission publications are listed in Appendix Five.

Target: To have completed consultation on an integrated Code of Practice on employment

Result: Target deferred, pending implementation of EU Directives and Single Equality Bill

Preparatory work on this objective and some preliminary consultation was undertaken. Work on the project will be taken forward in the context of the development of single equality legislation and the implementation of the EU equality Directives, which will affect the content of any Code, and the consideration of the production of a wider range of employment-related Codes.

Target: To have published a Code of Practice for service providers under the DDA

Result: Target deferred, pending production of regulations

Our draft Code of Practice for service providers, revised in light of the new duties on physical access to goods, facilities and services had been submitted to OFMDFM for approval in March 2001. OFMDFM is considering a complex issue about the link with building regulations before bringing forward the Disability Discrimination (Provider of Services) (Adjustment of Premises) Regulations. By year end this had not been resolved and we were not therefore in the position to finalise the draft Code for publication.

We are aware that small businesses have concerns about the DDA and so, in partnership with the Disability Rights Commission, we produced a practical guide for small businesses on how to implement physical alterations to premises in advance of 2004. The Federation of Small Businesses has endorsed the guide and undertaken to promote it among its members. Research carried out with the Disability Rights Commission in Great Britain explored the costs and benefits of making the reasonable adjustments requires by the Act. The majority of service providers who had made adjustments found that the associated benefits were greater than or equal to the costs. The dissemination of the guide and these survey findings supporting the cost-effectiveness of adjustments, will form a central plank of the Commission's strategy for raising awareness of the access Code and its implementation in 2004.

A clear picture of the need for the DDA was given by our research project into disabled people's experiences of service provision. It showed that shopping was most likely to present difficulties; and that, sadly, few people had been given any help to overcome those difficulties. This information has been brought to the attention of the Employers' Forum on Disability and the business sector to help them address barriers to services. We have also held discussion with transport providers to ensure access to shopping centres.

Target: To have published a racial equality Code of Practice on housing, and good practice guides on health and education

Result: Target met

The good practice guide to racial equality in education is an important resource for policy makers and practitioners in the education system. It marked the beginning of a partnership with the Department and the Minister of Education that led to a conference on racial equality in education and a draft action plan for taking this work forward.

We have also concentrated efforts on racial equality and health, which led to the production of the good practice guide to racial equality in health, endorsed by the Minister for Health, Social Services and Public Safety.

In the area of housing and accommodation the Commission launched a consultative draft of the first Code of Practice on racial equality in housing.

Objective: To promote affirmative/positive action and reasonable adjustments

Performance Indicator: Uptake and implementation of affirmative/positive action measures; compliance with statutory monitoring requirements; adoption of reasonable adjustments; changes in employment patterns and trends

Target: To have developed an action plan on equal pay

Result: Target met

An action plan was developed and a programme of work planned for the incoming year. Pay inequality remains an enduring feature of many women's employment; following the Equal Pay Task Force report in February 2001 and subsequent work on pay audits across the UK, the issue regained sharp focus. The Commission is committed to tackling this inequality, building on work already ongoing in Great Britain.

We are also participating in a European Commission funded project on developing sectoral strategies to address gender pay gaps, in partnership with Ireland, Finland and Sweden. The study aims to explore the gender pay gap in certain sectors; we in Northern Ireland are managing research in retail and information technology. We aim to identify strategies and actions to reduce pay gaps. Approaching the pay gap by concentrating on particular sectors has the potential to contribute substantially to achieving greater gender equality in employment. The research will analyse the pay gap in the IT and retail sectors, identify the factors which contribute to the pay gaps and develop proposals to tackle the problem.

Target: To have ensured at least 90% compliance with new FETO monitoring provisions

Result: Target met

• **Monitoring**

During this period 39 employers, out of the 3825 registered with the Commission, failed to comply with the monitoring regulations. Of these, 26 were prosecuted and a further

13 were awaiting prosecution. This represents a 99% level of compliance with only 1% of registered employers not complying with the statutory requirements.

This was the first year that employers had to provide monitoring information in line with the Fair Employment (Monitoring) Regulations (NI) 1999. The Commission's approach to the compliance of statutory monitoring has always been to provide advice and assistance to all and to use enforcement provisions only as a last resort. We therefore continue to offer advice and support to employers to ensure that they can comply with the new requirements placed on them. This includes training and responding to individual requests for help. The number of monitoring enquiries increased significantly with the introduction of these new regulations. The increase is largely to do with definitions of part-time, appointee and promotee.

The Standard Occupational Classification used to classify occupations in the monitoring return form was amended this year to reflect the classifications used in the 2001 Census. In order to do this the fair employment monitoring regulations will also require amendment. We will continue to work to ensure that employers get the advice they need to implement changes efficiently.

We began work on guidance material on qualitative and quantitative monitoring for all equality groups currently covered by anti-discriminatory legislation and s75. This guidance will cover monitoring for employment, goods, facilities and services and s75 equality impact assessments.

• Registration

One of the key employer duties is to register with the Commission. By the end of the year 3835 public and private sector companies were registered. This represents a small decrease in the previous year from 3899. We continue to make available this Register of Employers.

• Reviews

Guidance material to assist organisations to complete their Article 55 reviews was adapted in line with the new monitoring provisions. In this period the Commission requested reviews from the 31 employers with more than 100 employees (there are 539 concerns in this size-range in Northern Ireland), who had not previously submitted a review. A further 53 employers in the same category submitted reviews voluntarily. Of these 84 reviews, 70 were in compliance with the legislation when we received them. The remaining 14 were brought into compliance following advice and support from Commission staff. Forty-nine of the 84 employers were given advice on policies, practices and procedures.

Target: To have ensured that at least 90% of employers show good faith efforts in implementing affirmative action agreements

Result: Target met

At the end of the year the Commission had affirmative action agreements in place with 313 employers; 241 were voluntary and the rest were legally enforceable. During the year the Commission agreed affirmative action programmes with 17 employers. Thirteen of these were from the target group of those with 51-100 employees, while

there were three large private sector employers and one public sector organisation where under representations were identified in the workforce.

We continue to help employers effectively implement their affirmative action agreements; this includes individual meetings to review the progress, input to seminars and the development of employer networks. This year, for example, we gave advice and support on implementing affirmative action programmes to a group of private sector employers in the Belfast area.

The Commission considered progress with 98 employers with affirmative action programmes in place. We are pleased that 96 (98%) of these employers made satisfactory good faith efforts on the implementation of their affirmative action programmes and it was decided that no further action under the legislation was required. The remaining two employers (2%) were required to take specific action to implement their agreements.

• Policing

The Commission, with its predecessor bodies, has extensive experience in working with the police to tackle under-representations in employment, and supported the recommendations in the Patten report and the subsequent Implementation Plan. We maintain our strategic interest in, and continue to make a significant contribution to, policing issues.

The first recruitment competition for police trainees, under the unique provisions of the Police (Northern Ireland) Act 2000 took place in the spring of 2001. The Commission was pleased to note that the applicant rates from Roman Catholics (36.5%) and from women (40.7%) were higher than had ever been achieved in the past. In the incoming year we will continue to work with the police on the development of a programme of action specifically targeting applicants who are Roman Catholic, women and/or from minority ethnic backgrounds.

The Commission also responded to the draft code on the appointment of Independent Members to District Police Partnerships. We were disappointed that so few women are on the Policing Board and wish to see District Police Partnerships being representative of the whole community, including women, those from minority ethnic backgrounds, those with disabilities and from the other s75 groups.

Meetings also took place with the Office of the Oversight Commissioner to discuss implementation of the Patten recommendations as they relate to recruitment, training and the working environment.

Given the importance of having a police service that is reflective of the whole community, we will continue our work on this important matter in the incoming year.

• Northern Ireland Civil Service

We continued to work with the civil service on a broad range of equal opportunities issues. The Commission met with the Senior Civil Service Review team, chaired by Lord Ouseley, and made a formal written submission on the development of strategies to

promote inclusivity and wider representation in the senior civil service. We look forward to the report of the review team and to contributing to the consultation process.

Target: To have implemented all employer-related activities in the Commission's action plan on recruitment for those not in employment

Result: Target met

As part of an initiative to tackle long-term unemployment, special provisions were introduced to the Fair Employment and Treatment (Northern Ireland) Order 1998, to make it lawful to give preference in recruitment and training to people who have not been in employment for a period of time. To encourage the use of this special provision, we worked closely with 186 employers, and held several focus group sessions with unemployed people to identify perceived barriers to employment and to raise awareness of the provision.

To highlight the issue and our work in this area, we held a major conference on employment and social inclusion for employers. The event, at which Will Hutton of the Work Foundation gave the keynote address, was opened by the Minister for Employment and Learning, and attended by 178 companies and community representatives. A follow-up series of meetings was held with employers and employment advisors. The conference was widely reported in the media, and the links established have greatly assisted our thinking on the problems around unemployment, employability and social inclusion.

We continue to advise Government on targets for measuring the reduction in unemployment, through our participation in the Taskforce on Employability, chaired by the Minister for Employment and Learning. We have contributed in particular to work on targets and indicators.

Target: To have developed an action plan to promote reasonable adjustments

Result: Target met

Research into knowledge of the Disability Discrimination Act among service providers in the retail, entertainment and finance sectors, uncovered a worryingly low level of awareness. The action plan comprised our highly successful "Louder than Words" campaign aimed at encouraging employers and service providers to take on the provisions of the DDA, by giving practical examples of reasonable adjustments. The campaign attracted over 800 employers and service providers. There was a 94% positive response to the question, "Was enough information given?" and 99.9% to, "Did the workshop meet your requirements?"

SUPPORTING PRIORITY ONE: Building Partnerships for Change

Objective: To maintain and develop effective partnerships and working arrangements with key organisations across Northern Ireland and internationally

Performance Indicators: Evidence of effective partnerships and communications

Target: To have developed and implemented a programme of outreach and partnership activities

Result: Target met

Our programme ranged widely across the sectors and groups affected by the equality legislation. A good deal of the work described in earlier sections of this report refers to joint initiatives. This section highlights some others and is arranged more or less geographically, starting closest to home.

We were delighted to welcome some notable equality experts from outside Northern Ireland who asked to meet with us to share ideas and experience in a way that enriches us all. They included Trevor Hall from the Home Office, the Chief Executive of the body with responsibility for equality in Bermuda, the representative of the British Council in Bulgaria, members of the Equal Opportunities Committee of the Scottish Parliament, and the Joint Committee on Human Rights.

• Northern Ireland

The Commission is determined to engage with stakeholders across Northern Ireland, not just in the Belfast area. In the year covered by this report, we held 26 events and initiatives outside Belfast, including training sessions, Commission meetings and consultations.

A pilot project linking the Commission with the Citizen's Advice Bureau and the Association of Independent Advice Centres was launched to develop an outreach disability advice service for people with disabilities and for employers and service providers. Over 150 advice workers were trained as part of the initiative, which took place in Omagh and Craigavon.

In order to bring forward partnership arrangements to sustain the s75 duties, new links were formed with networks such as the Chief Executives' Forum, the Association of Northern Ireland Colleges and the Local Government Equality Officers' Network. Relationships were also developed with new networks such as the Western Equality and Human Rights Forum in health and social services and the Equality Liaison Group in education. We set up the s75 UK Bodies Network, recognising that GB-based public authorities have some common interests in responding to the challenges in s75.

We continued to work closely with the Northern Ireland Human Rights Commission, and revised our Memorandum of Understanding to include reference to the need for our two Commissions to provide joint funding for legal complainants in some circumstances. We also held a constructive meeting to discuss the Bill of Rights and single equality legislation.

• North/South

We worked closely with colleagues from the Equality Authority throughout the year. The Authority held its Board meeting at Equality House in November, and shared a meeting with Commissioners. One of the Ministers with responsibility for equality hosted a dinner at Stormont.

Our partnership with the Equality Authority runs through our membership of the Equality and Human Rights Forum; membership of the European Advisory Committee on equal opportunities, chaired this year by the Equality Authority's Chief Executive Officer Niall Crowley; work on mainstreaming equality within the EQUAL programme; the joint research described in Strategic Priority One; and regular informal and mutually supportive communications.

The National Disability Authority visited the Commission in March 2002, part of a regular exchange of ideas and experience between the two bodies.

In partnership with the Equality Authority and the National Consultative Committee on Racism and Interculturalism, we held the second North/South roundtable in Newry. We took this opportunity to hear an update on the work of the European Monitoring Centre on Racism and Xenophobia with the Centre's Chair, Bob Purkiss, as guest speaker. We agreed in Newry that we would work together, North and South, to take forward the action plans arising out of the World Conference.

• GB and Ireland

Discussions have taken place with the Runnymede Trust about the inclusion of Northern Ireland in the next phase of the Future of Multi-Ethnic Britain initiative. Other partnership measures include RAXEN, where we are part of the UK national focal point.

The Joint Equality and Human Rights Forum is made up of the equality and human rights bodies in the UK and Ireland. This year, the group was joined by the Irish Human Rights Commission. The Forum met in June (hosted by the Disability Rights Commission in London) and in December (hosted by the Equality Authority in Dublin) and on both occasions had the opportunity to meet with government representatives. Topics discussed by the Chairs/Commissioners and Chief Executives of the agencies included multiple identity/discrimination; the interface between poverty and inequality; links with

the British and Irish Council; EU funding. Alongside these structural contacts, the staff of all the member bodies meet and work together as appropriate through the year.

- **European engagement**

European work to promote equality has had a significant impact in Northern Ireland. European Community law, in gender equality and more recently across the whole equality spectrum, has protected people from discrimination. Funding has opened up training and employment opportunities to many groups and individuals who could not otherwise access them, and the funding programmes' regulations increasingly demand an important level of equality-proofing. We contribute to the development of most of the EU funding programmes through being represented on an increasing number of monitoring committees.

We are partners in a trans-national race project with other specialist equality bodies in Britain, Ireland, the Netherlands, Sweden, Austria and Belgium. We continue to be core members of the UK Race and Europe Network. The Commission also participated in a programme funded by Jonkoping University in Sweden to facilitate post-ethnic-conflict projects in promoting good relations.

- **International**

The Commission was represented on the UK Government delegation at the UN World Conference against Racism held in Durban in South Africa. The UK Minister, Baroness Amos, referred to the Commission as playing "a vital, independent role in monitoring and enforcing anti-discrimination legislation." During the upcoming year we will be involved in the follow-up to Durban, as well as working on a Northern Ireland strategy and action plan, in partnerships with the BME sector and the NI Human Rights Commission.

Target: To have prepared and consulted on proposals for (a) consultative council(s)

Result: Target partly met

By year end, we had received the first results of the pre-consultative exercise we decided to carry out, to test the views of our stakeholders on how best to respond to section 74 of the Northern Ireland Act. This refers to the Commission having regard to advice offered by a consultative council. In the incoming year we will analyse these results and decide on how best to go forward on this issue.

Part of the pre-consultation exercise was to audit our existing partnership work, which is considerable. One effective example is our work with black and minority ethnic groups, where we held community consultations on the housing and accommodation Code of Practice in Craigavon, Derry/Londonderry and Belfast.

We have also looked at the principles of partnership, for example through research into women's educational disadvantage. This examined current and potential partnership working between women's community education and further education. It provides an excellent framework for establishing partnerships and making them work.

SUPPORTING PRIORITY TWO: Developing Organisational Effectiveness

Objective: To implement new organisational structure and harmonise policies and procedures

Performance Indicator: New structure in place

Target: To have completed staff moving to new structure

Result: Target met

Re-structuring continued according to plan during the year, and the Commission now operates in three Divisions - Legal Policy and Advice; Operations and Corporate Services; Policy and Public Affairs. They are headed by Barney McNeaney, Antoinette McKeown and, from 1 April 2002, Barry Fitzpatrick. Structurally, we kept a special focus on race and disability. This continues into the current year in a different format, with some functions moving to integrated teams, and others being retained in development units for a further period.

We also undertook a major change management programme to complete the task of fully integrating the Commission and its work. We formed three project teams - Information and Advice; Legal; Policy - on specific issues arising from integration in these areas. We also held workshops with the management teams to progress change management and to help us give an integrated and effective equality service.

Performance Indicator: Move to new building completed

Target: To have moved to new site

Result: Target met

The Commission officially accepted Equality House from the developer on Monday 23 July 2001 and moved staff and equipment to the new premises in early August. It was officially opened by Sir Reg Empey MLA and Séamus Mallon MP MLA on Monday 15 October 2001, with Jane Kennedy MP representing the Secretary of State. Over 200 representatives from the political, public service, business, trade union and NGO sectors within Northern Ireland, as well as equality bodies throughout the islands, came to help us celebrate this key event in the Commission's development.

The new building project and the move to the new site were completed to target and on time. As we had worked out of three sites for over a year, it made all the difference to staff to be together in one place, to have enough space, and to be able to offer the highest standards of physical access to staff and visitors.

Performance Indicator: Training action plan developed

Target: To have developed and implemented a training action plan

Result: Target met

Identifying organisational training needs in the early stages was a key area of concern for us and a review of training was undertaken this year. This identified training priorities and decisions on funding training courses in the year were based on these priorities. Staff undertook a wide range of training during the year, including: appraisal; coaching and teambuilding; excelling as a first time manager; supervision; report writing; impact assessment; Internet awareness; web page design; human rights and equality legislation; and anti-racism. A number of staff also undertook further education courses.

Performance Indicator: Number of policies and procedures in place

Target: To have completed the review of human resources and equality policies and procedures

Result: Target met

All existing human resources policies and procedures were reviewed, and seventeen new or revised policies were drafted, negotiated and agreed by management and the trade union.

Performance Indicator: Communications strategy in place; feedback from staff

Target: To have put in place an effective internal system

Result: Target met

An action plan and protocol for internal communications was agreed and implemented.

Performance Indicator: Frequency of meetings with Joint Consultative and Negotiating Committee

Target: To maintain effective employee relations

Result: Target met

Seven formal JCNC meetings were held along with informal discussions with NIPSA Branch 147 officials and full-time representatives as required.

Objective: To monitor and evaluate performance against objectives

Performance Indicator: Appropriate measurement systems in place

Target: To have finalised identification of relevant management information needs; to develop new management systems

Result: Target met

The migration of all IT and telecommunications equipment from three separate locations into Equality House was achieved with only eight hours downtime during which a limited service operated. This major project was successfully managed and implemented by Commission staff using their planning skills and technical expertise.

Identification of relevant management information needs in respect of financial information, operating plan targets and current business processes were completed in the following key areas:

- A comprehensive monitoring system to deal with employers' returns under the new regulations
- Integration of the Commission's financial systems; an integrated decision support system (VISION) was implemented enabling further development of the management accounting system
- A database for initial contacts, visits and training
- Advice and disability were added to the common employer contact system
- Phase 1 of a Commission wide legal enquiry system
- A reporting system for statutory duty equality impact assessment work
- A new monitoring reporting system for policy and research
- An improved personnel system

Performance Indicator: Regular reports to Commission, Chief Executive, Senior Management Team and OFMDFM

Target: To have implemented regular reporting mechanisms

Result: Target met

Reporting mechanisms are in place to report on a quarterly basis against the Operational Plan to the Commission, the Senior Management Team and the OFMDFM. In addition, the new Divisions have Divisional Plans to govern their work, drawn from the Operational Plan, and regular reports of progress are provided to the relevant Committees of the Commission. These cover finance, staffing, employers' monitoring returns, equality impact assessment, policy and research, and information and advice. Further work on developing new systems for measuring other areas of activity is aligned to future plans to meet projected management information needs.

Performance Indicator: Customer service benchmarks in place

Target: To have established customer service benchmarks and quality standards across all areas of service delivery

Result: Target deferred, pending integration work

This objective is inextricably linked to the integration project; work on this aspect of integration has gone on throughout the year and will continue next year.

Objective: To review and develop corporate and operational planning process, incorporating equality scheme and New TSN action plan

Performance Indicator: Review completed

Target: To have completed review and any changes

Result: Target met

An internal project group was formed in March 2002 to begin preparations for the next Corporate Plan (2003-2006), using the Balanced Scorecard methodology as a means of translating our strategic goals into objectives and targets using a balanced set of perspectives.

Performance Indicator: Equality scheme in place

Target: To consider responses to consultation on the equality scheme and finalise scheme

Result: Target partly met

The Commission completed the first draft of its equality scheme during the year under review and will continue to progress this work in the incoming year.

Performance Indicator: TSN action plan in place

Target: To have published New TSN action plan

Result: Target met

Our New Targeting Social Need (NTSN) Action Plan was consulted on and implemented this year. Systems have been established to ensure data collection and to facilitate the monitoring of the Commission targets. Quarterly reports on the implementation of the NTSN action plan are submitted to OFMDFM.

Photograph captions:-

- p13 Lord Lester of Herne Hill, key note speaker at “Mapping the Equality Agenda”
- p18 Launch of the draft Code of Practice on racial equality in housing and accommodation
- p24 Launch of the good practice guide to racial equality in health
- p28 Launch of the outreach disability advice service
- p29 At the Joint Equality Authority and Equality Commission dinner at Stormont
- p31 Sir Reg Empey MLA and Mr Séamus Mallon MP MLA officiating at the opening of Equality House

APPENDIX ONE

Commissioners

Joan Harbison
(Chief Commissioner)
(6)

Bronagh Hinds
(Deputy Chief Commissioner)
(5)

Harry Coll
(5)

Rosemary Connolly
(3)

Paul Donaghy
(6)

Alan Henry
(5)

John Heron
(6)

Jeremy Bryson
(4)

Ann Hope
(6)

Ruth Lavery
(6)

Stephen Livingstone
(5)

Margaret Logue
(4)

Shahid Malik
(2)

Harry McConnell
(5)

Robin Mullan
(4)

Robert Osborne
(3)

Richard Steele
(5)

Anna Lo
(5)

Monica Wilson
(4)

Noreen Wright
(4)

Numbers in brackets refer to Commission meetings attended, out of a total of six.

Commissioners also served on at least two sub-committees (Legal Funding; Legal Policy; Operations and Corporate Services; Policy and Public Affairs; Statutory Duty). Membership of these committees varied throughout the year.

APPENDIX TWO
ORGANISATION CHART
EQUALITY COMMISSION FOR NORTHERN IRELAND

Religious and gender composition of Equality Commission staff at 31 January 2002

	Protestant	Roman Catholic	Cannot be Determined	Female	Male	Total
	60 (42.3%) [44.1%]*	76 (53.5%) [55.9%]*	6 (4.2%)	104 (73.2%)	38 (26.8%)	142

These figures show a small increase in the under-represented male and Protestant groups in the workforce this year
 * monitored workforce

Appendix Three Legal complaints

Complaints statistics	Religion and politics	Race	Sex	Disability	Total
Legal complaints and enquiries	901	308	1144	328	2681
Applications granted assistance	289	100	160	112	661
Applications refused assistance	122	40	31	7	200
Applications withdrawn before consideration		6			6
Applications refused assistance after review	26	7		3	36
Applications withdrawn after review		2			2
Industrial/Fair Employment Tribunal Proceedings					
Cases settled	59	12	29	6	106
Cases heard and upheld	2	1	1	1	5
Cases heard and dismissed	6	1	4 (1 under Review)	2	13
County Court Proceedings					
Cases heard and upheld		1			1
Cases heard and dismissed		21			21
Cases settled	1	6		5	12
Other courts					
Court of Appeal Cases heard and upheld Cases heard and dismissed	1				1
High Court Heard and upheld Heard and dismissed		4			4
European Court Heard and upheld Heard and dismissed	1				1

SETTLEMENTS
(Disability)
1 April 2001 - 31 March 2002

Name of Case	Admission of Discrimination	Admission in relation to procedures	Apology/ Statement of Regret	Remedial Terms	Compensation	Nature of Case
Alan Bell -v- Conor Hughes t/a Doorstep Coffee House	✓	✓	✓	✓		Reasonable adjustment Goods facilities services
Harold Ogilby -v- F G Wilson (Engineering) Ltd	✓	✓	✓	✓	£15,000	Redundancy
Karen Coyle -v- First Trust Bank	✓	✓	✓	✓	£6,000	Reasonable adjustment
Patrick Duggan -v- UNISON	✓	✓	✓	✓	£5,000	Unfair dismissal
Marie Lynch -v- UGC Cinemas		✓	✓	✓		Goods facilities services
Dorothy Montgomery -v- (1) Langley Hall Svcs Ltd (2) Loughside Properties Ltd	✓	✓	✓	✓	£1,500	Reasonable adjustment Goods facilities services
Mary Patricia Hughes -v- MEPC Ltd & Galago Ltd t/a Centuryan		✓	✓		Legal fees & outlay £856 £172	Goods facilities services
Foster & Beggs -v- (1) Mark Coyle t/a Fealtys (2) Beannchor Ltd	✓	✓	✓		£4,000	Goods facilities services
Gertrude Johnston -v- Lidi NI Gmbh	✓	✓	✓	✓	£3,000	Goods facilities services
Frances McDowell -v- BIFHE & Prof P Murphy		✓	✓	✓	£1,500	Goods facilities services
Caitriona Murtagh -v- Action Cancer	✓	✓	✓	✓	£35,000	Redundancy
					£6,000	Termination

SETTLEMENTS
(Fair Employment)
1 April 2001 - 31 March 2002

Name of Case	Admission of Discrimination	Admission in relation to procedures	Apology/ Statement of Regret	Remedial Terms	Compensation	Nature of Case
Stephen Hunter -v- 1)MKL Meats 2) Arthur Laverty				✓	£7,500 (By 1st Resp)	Termination
David Snoddy -v- University of Ulster		✓		✓	£1,000	Recruitment & selection
Andrew Michael Dawson -v- University of Ulster		✓		✓	£1,000	Recruitment & selection
Gary Townley -v- South & East Belfast Social Services Trust		✓	✓	✓	£6,268	Recruitment & selection
Paul Swain -v- Securicor Cash Services			✓	✓	£5,000	Recruitment & selection
Joseph Reid -v- Ormeau Foods Ltd & Others			✓		£26,000	Redundancy
Deirdre Mortell -v- Oxfam				✓	£15,000	Recruitment & selection
Bronagh Flynn -v- Stranmillis University College			✓	✓	£1,898	Harassment (County Court)
Caitriona Devlin -v- Belfast City Hospital & Social Services Trust			✓	✓	£5,000	Recruitment & selection
Daniel Feeney -v- Mallusk Accident Repair Centre			✓	✓	£5,000	Sectarian harassment
Joseph Murtagh -v- B. E Aerospace (Seating Ltd)	✓	✓	✓	✓	£17,500	Sectarian harassment
Joseph McMenamy -v- F.G.Wilson					£20,000	Sectarian harassment

SETTLEMENTS

(Fair Employment)

1 April 2001 - 31 March 2002

Name of Case	Admission of Discrimination	Admission in relation to procedures	Apology/ Statement of Regret	Remedial Terms	Compensation	Nature of Case
Peter O'Hara -v- Chief Constable of the RUC & Superintendent Campbell					£5,000 (By 1st Resp)	Dismissal
Lucinda Mulholland -v- South Eastern Education & Library Board and the Governing Body at Parkview Special School	✓	✓	✓	✓	£10,000	Recruitment & selection
Ignatius McGowan -v- North Eastern Education & Library Board	✓	✓	✓	✓	£6,000	Recruitment & selection
Patrick Murray -v- Belfast City Council X 2 cases			✓	✓	£5,000	Victimisation
Joseph Devlin -v- Miles-Ash Ltd Darrell McKnight, Raymond Murphy & Michael Dickinson			✓ (By 1st Resp)	✓ (By 1st Resp)	£6,000 (By 1st Resp)	Sectarian harassment
Stephen Hegney -v- Dessian Products Ltd			✓	✓	£2,000	Sectarian harassment
Mairead Campbell -v- Moyolla Cellars Ltd			✓	✓	£3,500	Sectarian harassment
Donald Wilson -v- Musgrave Supervalu Centra (NI) Ltd	✓	✓	✓	✓	£50,000	Recruitment & selection

SETTLEMENTS
(Fair Employment)
1 April 2001 - 31 March 2002

Name of Case	Admission of Discrimination	Admission in relation to procedures	Apology/ Statement of Regret	Remedial Terms	Compensation	Nature of Case
Kenneth Harland -v- Regal Processors Ltd & American Protein Corporation				✓ (By 1st Resp)	£5,500 (By 1st Resp)	Less favourable treatment: employment
Thomas McDonnell -v- Servisair (UK) Ltd	✓	✓	✓	✓	£5,000	Sectarian harassment
Peter Byrne -v- Coates of Ireland Ltd		✓	✓	✓	£8,000	Recruitment & selection
Joseph Armstrong -v- A.H. Foods t/a Andrews Milling			✓	✓	£20,000	Redundancy
Alex Hasson -v- Royal Mail & Walter Douglas		✓ (By 1st Resp)	✓ (By 1st Resp)	✓ (By 1st Resp)	£16,000 (By 1st Resp)	Sectarian harassment
Mark McCabe -v- Elevation Equipment Co & Others				✓ (By 1st Resp)	£2,900 (By 1st Resp)	Dismissal
Mary Turkington -v- North Eastern Education & Library Board		✓	✓	✓	£1,500	Recruitment & selection
Sharon Duffy -v- Craigavon Borough Council		✓	✓	✓	£12,500	Recruitment & selection
Patricia Ikram -v- Boots the Chemists Ltd, Sanofi Beaute Ltd				✓	£4,500	Recruitment & selection
Veronica Moore -v- Northern Health & Social Services Board	✓		✓	✓	£30,000	Sectarian harassment
Jacqueline Tweedie -v- Mary Quinn t/a Costcutter			✓	✓	£1,500	Recruitment & selection
Conor McAleenan -v- Short Brothers PLC				✓	£2,500	Less favourable treatment

SETTLEMENTS
 (Fair Employment)
 1 April 2001 - 31 March 2002

Name of Case	Admission of Discrimination	Admission in relation to procedures	Apology/ Statement of Regret	Remedial Terms	Compensation	Nature of Case
Paul King -v- Woodside Haulage Ltd		✓	✓	✓	£6,000	Recruitment & selection
Denis Kelly -v- Sydney Pentland Ltd		✓	✓	✓	£25,000	Sexist harassment
Peter Brown -v- N.I. Ambulance Service & Health & Social Services Executive x 2 cases		✓ (By 2nd Resp)	✓ (By 2nd Resp)	✓ (By 2nd Resp)	£3,000 (By 2nd Resp)	Recruitment & selection
Sadhbh Branton -v- Julie's Kitchen	✓		✓	✓	£5,000	Sexist harassment
David Lundy -v- EIS Ltd & Harland & Wolff (SHI) PLC	✓	✓	✓ (By 2nd Resp)	✓ (By 2nd Resp)	£7,500 (By 2nd Resp)	Sexist harassment
Ronald Millican -v- Diamond Recruitment	✓	✓	✓	✓	£35,000	Sexist harassment
Daniel James Connor -v- Ballymoney Borough Council		✓	✓	✓	£7,500	Recruitment & selection
Paul Murray -v- Rockall Seafoods Ltd		✓		✓	£4,000	Redundancy
Paul Lonsdale -v- Henry Denny & Sons (NI) Ltd	✓	✓	✓	✓	£6,269	Sexist harassment
Barbara Higginson -v- Eurocar UK Limited X 2 cases		✓	✓	✓	£6,000	Recruitment & selection
Mark McGuinness -v- Initial City Link		✓	✓	✓	£12,500	Sexist harassment
Thomas Davis -v- ACC Distribution	✓	✓	✓	✓	£3,500	Sexist harassment

SETTLEMENTS
 (Fair Employment)
 1 April 2001 - 31 March 2002

Name of Case	Admission of Discrimination	Admission in relation to procedures	Apology/ Statement of Regret	Remedial Terms	Compensation	Nature of Case
Frances McDowell -v- BIFHE & Professor P Murphy X 2 cases			✓ (By 1st & 2nd Resp)	✓ (By 1st Resp)	£35,000	Less favourable treatment: Employment
Grace McGrath -v- 1) Dr Anthony Malcolmsom 2) Dept of the Environment	✓		✓	✓ (By 2nd Resp)	£20,000	Sectarian harassment
Hugh O'Neill -v- Stranmillis University College			✓	✓	£15,000	Recruitment & selection
Mark Fitzpatrick -v- MOD					£5,000	Sectarian harassment
Patrick O Smith -v- MOD X 2 cases			✓		£20,000	Recruitment & selection & harassment
Alan Ross Hakin -v- Readymix NI Ltd & RMC Group Services & Others X 2 cases		✓ (By 1st Resp)	✓ (By 1st Resp)	✓	£6,000 (By 1st Resp)	Sectarian harassment & Victimisation
William McCaul -v- Kedington (NI) Ltd		✓		✓	£2,500	Termination
Charles Magill -v- Kedington (NI) Ltd		✓		✓	£1,500	Termination
Anthony Shirton -v- Kedington (NI) Ltd		✓		✓	£2,500	Termination
Joseph Bowers -v- MSF					£51,430	Less favourable treatment: Employment

SETTLEMENTS

(Race)
1 April 2001 - 31 March 2002

Name of Case	Admission of Discrimination	Admission in relation to procedures	Apology/ Statement of Regret	Remedial Terms	Compensation	Nature of Case
Deirdre Mortell -v- Oxfam			✓	✓	£15,000*	Recruitment & selection
Anna Trinquet -v- Botanic Inns			✓	✓	£18,000*	Racial harassment
Mrs Ho -v- Driver Vehicle Licensing Agency			✓	✓	None, received an ex-gratia payment of £50 towards interpreter's fee	Goods facilities services
Sanchez Ros, Geraldo Garcia Rodriguez, Nevis Francesca Martin, Rachael Diez Garcia -v- Bettercare	✓		✓	✓	£2,550 to each applicant	Less favourable treatment: Employment
Ann Pryor -v- Corporate Wardrobe	✓		✓	✓	£14,000	Dismissal
Jason Duplock v- Isaac Agnew Ltd and others				✓	£5,000	Harassment
Deborah Horsman and Ivan Brown -v- Seatruck Ferries					£25,000 for each applicant and costs	Less favourable treatment: Employment
Katina Kraemar -v- Blackstar UK				✓	£4,500	Redundancy
Michael Stokes and John McDonagh -v- Quigley's Bar					£300 each and £500 towards plaintiffs' costs	Less favourable treatment: Goods facilities services
Martin Ward, John McDonagh, Edward McDonagh -v- Harry Hoots	✓				£1,000 plus costs for each plaintiff	Goods facilities services

SETTLEMENTS

(Race)
1 April 2001 - 31 March 2002

Name of Case	Admission of Discrimination	Admission in relation to procedures	Apology/ Statement of Regret	Remedial Terms	Compensation	Nature of Case
Alison Meshida -v- Police Authority for NI		✓		✓	£8,500	Less favourable treatment: Employment
Peter Smyth -v- Meteorological Office	✓	✓	✓		£20,000	Recruitment & selection

SETTLEMENTS

(Sex)
1 April 2001 - 31 March 2002

Name of Case	Admission of Discrimination	Admission in relation to procedures	Apology/ Statement of Regret	Remedial Terms	Compensation	Nature of Case
Katrina Newcombe -v- McDonald's Restaurant Ltd			✓		£22,500	Sexual harassment
Violet Hume -v- Industrial Therapy Organisation					£17,500	Sexual harassment
Anna Trinquet -v- Botanic Inns Ltd					£18,000	Harassment
Joyce Thompson -v- P D Vending Ltd				✓	£30,000	Less favourable treatment: Employment
Maureen Caves -v- Northern Ireland Prison Service				✓	£6,000	Recruitment & selection
Sinead Cahill -v- Just Kids Private Day Nursery					£4,750	Pregnancy/maternity & dismissal
Tracey Kane -v- The Shirt Makers Guild Ltd			✓		£5,750	Pregnancy/maternity
Ava Martin -v- MOD				✓	£3,500	Pregnancy/maternity & dismissal
Caroline Pennie -v- Daewoo			✓		£5,000	Pregnancy/maternity
Caron Fisher -v- Abbey National Plc					£3,000	Family friendly practices
Joyce Thompson -v- P D Vending Ltd				✓	£3,000	Victimisation
Rachel Lawrey -v- British Home Stores Plc			✓		£6,750	Pregnancy/maternity & Victimisation
Geraldine McCann -v- Delta Print & Packaging Ltd			✓		£10,000	Sexual harassment

SETTLEMENTS

(Sex)
1 April 2001 - 31 March 2002

Name of Case	Admission of Discrimination	Admission in relation to procedures	Apology/ Statement of Regret	Remedial Terms	Compensation	Nature of Case
Lorraine Johnston -v- Grove Services			✓	✓	£9,000	Pregnancy/maternity
Heather McIlwaine -v- The Planter's Tavern					£9,000	Pregnancy/maternity
Pamela Couser -v- Deloitte & Touche			✓	✓	£10,000	Family friendly practices
Sheelagh Kennedy -v- NI Tourist Board					£3,000	Recruitment & selection
Barbara Ann Hitchens -v- M B McGrady & Co					£1,300	Pregnancy/maternity
Tracey Mornin -v- NPO UK Ltd				✓	£7,200	Pregnancy/maternity
Marion Burgess -v- Holywood Nursing Home			✓		£6,000	Family friendly practices.
Lorraine Parkinson -v- Netcom Communications Ltd			✓		£4,500	Pregnancy/maternity
Michelle Long -v- (1) Brian McDermott (2) Burger King			✓	✓	£4,500	Less favourable treatment: Employment
Ian Harrison -v- (1) Schrader Electronics (2) First Choice Selection Services				✓	£1,300	Sexual harassment & Victimisation
Catherine Whelan -v- Gerald McAuley			✓	✓	£3,000	Family friendly practices
Susan Kirk -v- (1) Combined Insurance Co of America (2) Harry Williamson			✓	✓	£8,250	Sexual harassment

SETTLEMENTS

(Sex)
1 April 2001 - 31 March 2002

Name of Case	Admission of Discrimination	Admission in relation to procedures	Apology/ Statement of Regret	Remedial Terms	Compensation	Nature of Case
Sharon Hall -v- Ulster Television			✓	✓	£42,500	Equal pay, dismissal & Victimisation
Deirdre Mortell -v- Oxfam					£15,000*	Recruitment & selection
Lisa Rahim -v-Resource Centre, Derry					£7,000	Redundancy/ Victimisation
Gaye Partridge, Michelle Ferry -v-Crane Stockholm Valve Ltd			✓	✓	£6,500 each	Equal pay
Audrey Hunter -v- Chief Constable RUC & Supt. Meek		✓	✓		£1,000	Recruitment & selection
Andrea Owen -v- Café Kylemore Ltd			✓	✓	£3,000	Pregnancy
Geraldine McCann -v- 1) Terry Cross 2) Delta Print & Packaging Ltd 3) Colin Bradley	✓		✓	✓	£10,000	Sexual harassment
Jacqueline Lorimer -v- MOD & Brian Somers	✓		✓	✓	£15,000	Sexual harassment
Tracey Kane -v- Robin Eagleson t/a/ The Shirtmakers Guild			✓	✓	£5,750	
Donna Conn -v- Hunter Simms Engineering Ltd				✓	£5,000	Equal pay/ Victimisation
Laura McMahon -v- NI Ambulance Service, Maurice Bingham, Gabriel McClean			✓		£22,000	Sexual harassment

APPENDIX FOUR

Financial assistance

Under Article 44 of the Race Relations Order and Article 55 of the Sex Discrimination Order, the Commission awards financial assistance for educational and research activities which promote equality of opportunity. Much of the research work carried out during the year is described in the body of the report. This appendix lists other projects given this assistance. Most are educational; research projects are identified as such.

Race Equality

An Droichead	Clár Éagsulachta An Droichead Intercultural programme of workshops
Belfast Islamic Centre	Islam season Exhibition and promotional activities
Belfast Travellers Education and Development Group	Voices unheard project Research programme on Traveller children
Derry Travellers Support Group	Traveller capacity building programme
Dungannon Portuguese Community	Dungannon Portuguese project Publication and dissemination of health promotion materials
Falls Women's Centre	West Belfast Health and Advocacy Project Major health study and benefits uptake campaign in Greater West Belfast area (research)
Future Voices	Getting Your Voice Heard Racial awareness training
Holywell Trust	Workshop on refugee and asylum seekers Asylum seekers and refugees workshop
Indian Community Centre	Representation at UN World Conference on Racism in Durban
Mandarin Speakers Association	Chinese art exhibition Chinese visual arts facilitation workshops
Multi-Cultural Resource Centre	Asylum seekers and refugees in Northern Ireland Needs assessment research

Multi-Cultural Resource Centre	Refugee Support Group Publication of refugee and asylum seeker media pack
Náiscoil Ard Mhacha	Clár Idrchultúrtha 2002 Racial equality training in Armagh; Irish and English medium projects
Northern Ireland Pakistani Cultural Association	Pakistani community Awareness evening on the Pakistani community in Northern Ireland
Northern Ireland African Cultural Centre	Cultural acceptance, exploration and diversity
Northern Ireland Citizens Advice Bureau	Advice for All project Outreach of CAB services to the Chinese Community
Northern Ireland Council for Ethnic Minorities	Annual Human Rights and Equality conference. The implications of Article 13 of the Amsterdam Treaty; and the proposed new Single Equality Bill
Northern Ireland Council for Ethnic Minorities	Regional conference Health issues affecting asylum seekers in Northern Ireland
Northern Ireland Council for Ethnic Minorities	Anti Racism Conference
Northern Ireland Council for Ethnic Minorities	Women's Conference
Northern Ireland Filipino Association	Education and development residential Evaluation of Association's work to date
Oi-Wah Womens Group	Education and training programme
St Columb's Park House	North/South initiative Anti racism in Ireland conference 2001
Travellers Movement (Northern Ireland)	Action research project Examining nomadism in Ireland

European Week against Racism 2002

Belfast Islamic Centre	Islamic awareness day
Belfast Travellers Support Group	Travellers conflict mediation pack launch
Chinese Welfare Association	Chinese cultural awareness open day
Cineversity	Screening of Mississippi Masala at QFT
Indian Community Centre	Anti-racism training for all
Latino América Unida	Cultural awareness workshop
Multi-Cultural Resource Centre	Computer training
Northern Ireland African Cultural Centre	African cultural workshops
Northern Ireland Council for Ethnic Minorities	Community workers' anti-racism training
Northern Ireland Council for Ethnic Minorities	Consultation seminar on Immigration and Asylum

Gender Equality

Belfast Women's Training Services	Making human rights work for women Conference to debate the Bill of Rights
Women into Politics	Dialogue across the City Help with transport costs for an election special at Parliament Buildings
Women into Politics	Bosnia exchange visit Cost of interpretation for visiting Bosnian women politicians
Women's Regional Consultative Forum	Development of a strategic and operating plan
Women's Resource & Development Agency	North/South research collaboration group - policy seminar Seminar with policy makers

APPENDIX FIVE

Publications

Annual Report 2000-2001

Are you an employer? (disability)

Article 55 Review Report Structure (revised)

Article 55 Review Report Structure for small organisations (revised)

Betty the builder, Neil the nurse - sex typing of occupations in primary schools

Betty the builder, Neil the nurse - sex typing of occupations in primary schools, summary report

Code of Practice - Fair employment in Northern Ireland chapter 5 (excerpts)

Disability discrimination in Northern Ireland

Do you have a disability?

11th Monitoring Report for Northern Ireland - a profile of the Northern Ireland workforce

Frequently asked questions about disability in employment

Good practice guide to promoting racial equality in planning for Travellers - consultation document

Guide to statutory duties arising from section 75 (revised)

Making access to goods and services easier for disabled customers - a practical guide for small businesses and other small service providers

New Targeting Social Needs action plan consultation

Practical guidance on equality impact assessment (revised)

Profile of 2000 monitoring returns - factsheet

Racial discrimination in Northern Ireland

Racial equality in education - conference report (joint project)

Racial equality in housing and accommodation Code of Practice - consultation document

Racial equality and health - good practice guidelines

Recommendations to OFMDFM on eliminating small employers' threshold under DDA 1005

Religious and political discrimination in Northern Ireland

Sex discrimination and equal pay in Northern Ireland

Single Equality Bill: position paper

Single Equality Bill: further considerations

Typically atypical: changing patterns of employment - the implications for gender equality

A wake up call on race: implications of the MacPherson Report for institutional racism in Northern Ireland

Your Equality Commission (revised)

APPENDIX SIX Commission Events

DATE	EVENT	LOCATION
03 April 01	Recruitment & selection seminar	Belfast
05 April 01	Harassment seminar	Belfast
10 April 01	Recruitment & selection seminar	Belfast
24 April 01	Article 55 seminar	Belfast
26 April 01	Recruitment & selection seminar	Belfast
01 May 01	Harassment seminar	Belfast
10 May 01	Recruitment seminar	Belfast
15 May 01	Harassment seminar	Belfast
17 May 01	Recruitment & selection seminar	Londonderry
22 May 01	Article 55 seminar	Belfast
23 May 01	Social inclusion conference	Belfast
24 May 01	Harassment seminar	Derry
31 May 01	Recruitment & selection seminar	Belfast
05 June 01	Louder than Words roadshow	Omagh
05 June 01	Harassment seminar	Belfast
06 June 01	Article 55 seminar	Belfast
07 June 01	Race Equality Forum	Belfast
07 June 01	Article 55 seminar	Craigavon
12 June 01	Louder than Words roadshow	Limavady
12 June 01	Recruitment & selection seminar	Craigavon
14 June 01	Recruitment & selection seminar	Belfast
18 June 01	Disability Employers Threshold	Belfast
18 June 01	Launch employment threshold	Belfast
19 June 01	Louder than Words roadshow (2 events am and pm)	Belfast
19 June 01	Introduction to gender seminar	Belfast
20 June 01	Commission meeting	Londonderry
21 June 01	Recruitment & selection seminar	Belfast
25 June 01	N/S Research joint launch	Belfast
26 June 01	Article 55 seminar	Belfast
26 June 01	Recruitment & selection seminar	Belfast
26 June 01	Louder than Words roadshow (2 events am and pm)	Airport Hotel
26 June 01	NIACAB Outreach disability initiative	Omagh
28 June 01	Harassment seminar	Craigavon
03 July 01	Louder than Words roadshow	Belfast
21 Aug 01	Recruitment & selection seminar	Belfast
23 Aug 01	Article 55 seminar	Derry
23 Aug 01	Harassment seminar	Belfast
30 Aug 01	Intro to equality seminar	Belfast
11 Sep 01	Recruitment & selection training	Londonderry
18 Sep 01	Disability outreach launch	Craigavon
20 Sep 01	Race Housing Code of Practice	Belfast
20 Sep 01	Intro to gender	Belfast

25 Sep 01	Equality Impact Assessment training	Equality House
15 Oct 01	Official opening Equality House	Equality House
16 Oct 01	First annual Equality Conference	Belfast
19 Oct 01	Equality Impact Assessment training	Derry
22 Oct 01	Race Equality Forum	Equality House
05 Nov 01	MSP visit	Equality House
05 Nov 01	Community relations consultation	Equality House
6/7 Nov 01	Equality Authority Board visit	Equality House
08 Nov 01	Race joint conference Dept Education	Kells
13 Nov 01	Harassment at work seminar	Belfast
14 Nov 01	Screening training for F&HE Colleges	Equality House
15 Nov 01	Recruitment & selection seminar	Belfast
16 Nov 01	Equality Impact Assessment training	Craigavon
20 Nov 01	Harassment at work seminar	Belfast
21 Nov 01	Disability discrimination seminar	Belfast
21 Nov 01	SEB briefing/consultation	Equality House
22 Nov 01	SEB briefing/consultation	Equality House
22 Nov 01	Article 55 seminar	Belfast
23 Nov 01	SEB briefing/consultation	Omagh
27 Nov 01	Disability discrimination seminar	Belfast
27 Nov 01	SEB briefing/consultation	Armagh
28 Nov 01	Refugee/asylum seekers conference	Belfast
28 Nov 01	Equality Impact Assessment training	Omagh
29 Nov 01	Harassment seminar	Belfast
29 Nov 01	SEB briefing/consultation	Coleraine
04 Dec 01	Racial discrimination seminar	Belfast
04 Dec 01	Equality Impact Assessment training	Equality House
05 Dec 01	SEB briefing/consultation	Londonderry
5/6 Dec 01	N/S conference on race	Newry
06 Dec 01	Intro to gender seminar	Belfast
11 Dec 01	Recruiting fairly seminar	Belfast
11 Dec 01	SEB conference	Belfast
13 Dec 01	Intro to equality seminar	Belfast
15 Jan 02	Equality Impact Assessment training	Newry
24 Jan 02	Launch of PWC research	Equality House
29 Jan 02	Harassment at work	Belfast
05 Feb 02	Recruiting fairly seminar	Belfast
07 Feb 02	Article 55 Review	Belfast
12 Feb 02	Equality Impact Assessment training	Ballymena
12 Feb 02	Introduction to gender equality	Belfast
14 Feb 02	Harassment at work	Belfast
19 Feb 02	Recruiting fairly seminar	Belfast
21 Feb 02	Disability Discrimination Act	Belfast
26 Feb 02	Article 55 Review	Belfast
26 Feb 02	Launch of Practical Guide for small businesses and service providers	Belfast
26 Feb 02	Code of Practice on Housing seminar	Belfast
26 Feb 02	Statutory Duty seminar for UK bodies	London
27 Feb 02	Racial equality in education report launch	Belfast
05 Mar 02	Harassment at work	Derry

07 Mar 02	Racial discrimination	Belfast
14 Mar 02	Harassment at work	Belfast
18 Mar 02	Launch of race equality Good Practice Guide on health care	Belfast
18 Mar 02	Anti-racism week (European week)	Belfast
19 Mar 02	Article 55 Review	Londonderry
21 Mar 02	UN Day (anti-racism initiative with NCCRI)	Belfast
28 Mar 02	Disability Discrimination Act seminar	Belfast

APPENDIX SEVEN

Responses to consultation documents

If you would like further information on any of these responses, please contact the Commission.

April 2001

Building the way forward in primary care
Work and parents Green Paper
Carriage of guide, hearing and assistance dogs in taxis

May 2001

Investing for health

June 2001

Student finance review

August 2001

Review of public library services
Regulations governing parental leave
A framework for simplification of the rules governing maternity pay and leave
Promoting Social Inclusion - consultation on future priorities

September 2001

A common funding formula for grant aided schools
Single Equality Bill

October 2001

A Commissioner for Children
The Task Force on Employability and Long-term Unemployment
Urban regeneration in Northern Ireland
Inquiry into early years provision

November 2001

Adoptive leave, paternity leave
Acute Hospitals Review Group report
Community relations policy
Programme for Government - 2002-2003

December 2001

Single Equality Bill
Public procurement policy

January 2002

Protection from sectarian and religious hatred in Scotland
European transport policy for 2010

February 2002

About time: flexible working (Work and Parents Taskforce)
Improving civil rights for disabled people - Northern Ireland Executive
Response to Disability Rights Task Force

March 2002

Towards Equality and Diversity - Article 13 European Directives in GB

**Equality Commission
for Northern Ireland**

Financial Statement

For the 12 months ended 31st March 2002

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Foreword to the Accounts

The Equality Commission for Northern Ireland is an executive non-departmental public body sponsored by the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister. The Commission, established on 1st October 1999 under the Northern Ireland Act 1998, assumed, along with additional responsibilities for statutory equality duties and disability matters, the duties and responsibilities of three former Commissions:

The Commission for Racial Equality for Northern Ireland
The Equal Opportunities Commission for Northern Ireland and
The Fair Employment Commission.

These accounts are prepared in accordance with Schedule 8(2) of the Northern Ireland Act 1998 and the Transfer of Rights and Liabilities (Northern Ireland) Order 1999 and in a form directed by the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister with the approval of the Department of Finance and Personnel.

Important Events Occurring After the Year End

There have been no significant events since the year-end, which would affect these accounts.

Results for the Year

The results for the Commission for the period are set out in detail on page 12. The deficit for the year was £28,659. This deficit includes additional costs in respect of the surrender of the lease of Andras House, our former offices, and the costs arising from the High Court action initiated by the landlord of the same premises in respect of a disputed charge for refurbishment.

Business Review

A full review of the activities of the Commission is given in the 2001/2002 Annual Report. The Commission has relocated to its new premises under a 10 year lease.

Fixed Assets

Details of the movements of fixed assets are set out in note 6 to the accounts.

Research and Development

The Equality Commission for Northern Ireland does not engage in any research and development activities as defined by GAAP.

Charitable Donations

The Commission made no charitable donations during the period.

Pension Liabilities

Staff Pension Liabilities are borne by the Principal Civil Service Pension Scheme (NI) - see notes 1 and 3 to the Accounts.

Payment to Suppliers

The Commission is committed to the prompt payment of bills for goods and services received in accordance with the Government's Better Payment Practice Code.

Unless otherwise stated in the contract, payment is due within 30 days of receipts of the goods or services, or presentation of a valid invoice or similar demand, whichever is later.

During the period 69% of bills were paid within this standard.

Given that this year was exceptional in that the Commission;

- was operating from 3 sites
- during the year relocated to a single site and
- had a significant re-organisation of staff,

the Commission accepts that this rate of payment was unacceptable and has taken steps to significantly improve the promptness in payments to creditors.

Disabled Persons

The Equality Commission seeks to follow best practice guidance as set out in Disability Codes of Practice, on employment and the provision of services to disabled persons.

Equality of Opportunity

The Commission is committed to the provision of equality of opportunity and fair participation to all persons regardless of sex, marital status, religious belief, political affiliation/opinion, age, family status, ethnic or racial background, sexual orientation, disability, nationality or trade union membership. The Commission will, in all its actions, conform to both the letter and the spirit of the relevant equality legislation.

The Commission will provide equality of opportunity to all persons irrespective of whether or not there are legislative provisions in place.

Employee Involvement

The Commission encourages widespread consultation and exchange of information at all levels within the Commission. This is effected through staff briefings and the involvement of staff representatives on a Joint Consultative and Negotiating Committee.

Commission Members

The following served as members of the Equality Commission during the period:

Joan Harbison	Chief Commissioner
Bronagh Hinds	Deputy Chief Commissioner
Jeremy Bryson	
Harry Coll	
Rosemary Connolly	
Paul Donaghy	
Alan Henry	
John Heron	
Ann Hope	
Ruth Lavery	
Stephen Livingstone	
Margaret Logue	
Harry McConnell	
Shahid Malik	

Robin Mullan
Robert Osborne
Richard Steele
Anna Man-Wah Lo (formerly Watson)
Monica Wilson
Noreen Wright

Commissioners' Interests

An up to date register of Commissioners' interests is maintained by the Chief Executive as Accounting Officer and is available for inspection at the Commission's offices in Equality House, 7-9 Shaftesbury Square, Belfast, BT2 7DP.

Commission Offices

Equality House
7-9 Shaftesbury Square
Belfast
BT2 7DP

Auditor

Northern Ireland Audit Office
106 University Street
Belfast BT7 1EU

Signed by:

Evelyn Collins
Chief Executive and Accounting Officer

Statement of Commission's and Chief Executive's Responsibilities

Under Paragraph 7(2)(A) of Schedule 8 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998, the Commission is required to prepare a statement of accounts in the form and on the basis determined by the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister, with the approval of the Department of Finance and Personnel. The accounts are prepared on an accruals basis and must give a true and fair view of the Commission's state of affairs at the year-end and of its income and expenditure, total recognised gains and losses and cash flows for the year.

In preparing the accounts the Commission is required to:

- observe the Accounts Direction issued by the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister, including the relevant accounting and disclosure requirements, and apply suitable accounting policies on a consistent basis;
- make judgements and estimates on a reasonable basis;
- state whether applicable accounting standards have been followed and disclose and explain any material departures in the financial statements;
- prepare the financial statements on an ongoing concern basis, unless it is inappropriate to presume that the Commission will continue to operate.

The Accounting Officer of the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister has designated the Chief Executive of the Equality Commission for Northern Ireland as the Accounting Officer of the Commission. The Chief Executive's duties as Accounting Officer, including responsibility for the propriety and regularity of the public finances and for the keeping of proper records, are set out in the Non-Departmental Public Bodies Accounting Officer's Memorandum issued by the Department of Finance and Personnel.

Signed by:

Evelyn Collins
Chief Executive and Accounting Officer

Statement on Internal Control/Transitional Statement

As Accounting Officer, I have responsibility for maintaining a sound system of internal control that supports the achievements of the Commission's policies, aims and objectives, set by the legislation, the Commission and Ministerial direction, whilst safeguarding the public funds and Commission assets for which I am personally responsible, in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to me in Government Accounting Northern Ireland.

The system of internal control is designed to manage rather than eliminate the risk of failure to achieve policies, aims and objectives; it can therefore only provide reasonable and not absolute assurance of effectiveness.

The system of internal control is based on an ongoing process designed to identify the principal risks to the achievement of the Commission's policies, aims and objectives, to evaluate the nature and extent of those risks and to manage them efficiently, effectively and economically. The systems necessary to implement DFP guidance were put in place by March 2002. This takes account of the time needed to fully embed the processes which the Commission has agreed should be established, and to improve their robustness.

The Commission has carried out appropriate procedures to ensure that it has identified its objectives and risks and determined a control strategy for each of the significant risks. As a result, risk ownership will be allocated to the appropriate staff and the Commission has set out its attitude to risk in the achievement of its objectives.

The Commission has ensured that procedures are in place for verifying that risk management and internal control are regularly reviewed and reported on. There will be a full risk and control assessment before reporting on the year ending 31 March 2003. Risk management has been incorporated more fully into the corporate planning and decision making process of the Commission.

The Commission receives periodic reports concerning internal control. The appropriate steps are being taken to manage risks in significant areas of responsibility and monitor progress reports on key projects.

Following the identification of the Commission's key objectives and risks, further work is being done to bring more consistency to the way the Commission treats risks.

In addition to the actions mentioned above, in the coming year the Commission plans to:

- regularly review and update the record of risks facing the organisation;
- set up a system of key performance and risk indicators; and
- develop and maintain an organisation-wide risk register.

The Commission has an internal audit service, provided by the Internal Audit Unit of the Southern Health & Social Services Board, which operates to standards defined in the Government Internal Audit Manual. They submit reports, which include the Head of

Internal Audit's independent opinion on the adequacy and effectiveness of the Commission's system of internal control together with recommendations for improvement.

My review of the effectiveness of the system of internal control is informed by the work of the internal auditors and the executive managers within the Commission who have responsibility for the development and maintenance of the internal control framework, and comments made by the external auditors in their management letters and other reports.

During the year a serious weakness in the systems of internal control to manage future liabilities was identified. This resulted in a material overspend on legal fees in the current year and an unmanageable level of future potential liabilities. The Commission's Internal Audit team undertook additional work to help determine the size and scope of the problem. Work has been and is currently being undertaken as a priority to redress this situation. A new legal database has been designed which will form the basis for determining future liabilities and as an essential management tool in the level of assistance granted to future cases.

Signed by

Evelyn Collins
Chief Executive and Accounting Officer

The Certificate and Report of the Comptroller and Auditor General to the Northern Ireland Assembly

I certify that I have audited the financial statements on pages 12 to 27 under the Northern Ireland Act 1998. These financial statements have been prepared under the historical cost convention and the accounting policies set out on pages 16 and 17.

Respective responsibilities of the Equality Commission, the Chief Executive and Auditor

As described on page 6, the Equality Commission and Chief Executive are responsible for the preparation of the financial statements in accordance with the Northern Ireland Act 1998 and directions made thereunder by the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister and for ensuring the regularity of financial transactions. The Equality Commission and Chief Executive are also responsible for the preparation of the contents of the Annual Report. My responsibilities, as independent auditor, are established by statute and guided by the Auditing Practices Board and the auditing profession's ethical guidance.

I report my opinion as to whether the financial statements give a true and fair view and are properly prepared in accordance with the Northern Ireland Act 1998 and directions made thereunder by the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister and whether in all material respects the expenditure and income have been applied to the purposes intended by the Northern Ireland Assembly and the financial transactions conform to the authorities which govern them. I also report if, in my opinion, the Foreword is not consistent with the financial statements, if the Equality Commission has not kept proper accounting records, or if I have not received all the information and explanations I require for my audit.

I read the other information contained in the Annual Report and consider whether it is consistent with the audited financial statements. I consider the implications for my certificate if I become aware of any apparent misstatements or material inconsistencies with the financial statements.

I review whether the statement on pages 7 and 8 reflects the Equality Commission for Northern Ireland's compliance with the Department of Finance and Personnel's guidance "Corporate governance: statement on the system of internal control". I report if it does not meet the requirements specified by the Department of Finance and Personnel, or if the statement is misleading or inconsistent with other information I am aware of from my audit of the financial statements.

Basis of audit opinion

I conducted my audit in accordance with United Kingdom Auditing Standards issued by the Auditing Practices Board except that the scope of my work was limited as explained below.

An audit includes examination, on a test basis, of evidence relevant to the amounts, disclosures and regularity of financial transactions included in the financial statements. It also includes an assessment of the significant estimates and judgements made by the Equality Commission and Chief Executive in the preparation of the financial statements, and of whether the accounting policies are appropriate to the Equality Commission for Northern Ireland's circumstances, consistently applied and adequately disclosed.

I planned and performed my audit so as to obtain all the information and explanations which I considered necessary in order to provide me with sufficient evidence to give reasonable assurance that the financial statements are free from material misstatement, whether caused by error, or by fraud or other irregularity and that, in all material respects, the expenditure and income have been applied to the purposes intended by the Northern Ireland Assembly and the financial transactions conform to the authorities which govern them.

However the evidence available to me was limited because I could not confirm the accuracy of the future liability for legal fees as there was no system of control on which I could rely for the purpose of my audit. There were no other satisfactory audit procedures that I could adopt to confirm that the contingent liability was accurately estimated.

In forming my opinion I have also evaluated the overall adequacy of the presentation of information in the financial statements.

Qualified opinion arising from limitation in audit scope

In my opinion:

- except for any adjustments that might have been found to be necessary had I been able to obtain sufficient evidence concerning the Equality Commission's future liability for legal fees, the financial statements give a true and fair view of the state of affairs of the Equality Commission for Northern Ireland at 31 March 2002 and of the deficit, total recognised gains and losses and cash flows for the year then ended and have been properly prepared in accordance with Schedule 8 (7)(2) (b) of the Northern Ireland Act; and
- in all material respects the expenditure and income have been applied to the purposes intended by the Northern Ireland Assembly and the financial transactions conform to the authorities which govern them.

In respect alone of the limitation on my work relating to the future liability for legal fees:

- I have not obtained all the information and explanations that I considered necessary for the purpose of my audit; and
- I was unable to determine whether proper accounting records had been maintained.

Details of this matter are set out in paragraphs 1 to 4 of my report.

J M Dowdall
Comptroller and Auditor General
28 January 2003

Northern Ireland Audit Office
106 University Street
Belfast BT7 1EU

Report of the Comptroller and Auditor General on the Accounts of the Equality Commission for Northern Ireland for the year ended 31 March 2002

1. In order to combat discrimination and to promote equality the Equality Commission for Northern Ireland offers support to complainants in cases of alleged discrimination by funding the legal costs involved. During the period under review the Commission was committed to supporting some eleven hundred cases which had been contracted out to firms of solicitors. It may be several years before these cases are resolved and the element of the costs which are outstanding at 31 March 2002 represent a liability which will have to be met in future years. Expenditure charged in the 2001-2002 financial statements amounted to £1.05 million compared to an authorised cash budget originally of £550,000, which increased in year to £850,000, and to the accrued expenditure in the previous year of £654,000. As the Commission has stated in the Transitional Statement of Internal Control there was a serious weakness in the system of internal control which resulted in a material overspend on legal fees in the current year and an unmanageable level of future potential liabilities.
2. At present the Commission has no systems to identify existing liabilities before payment is demanded or to predict the liabilities which will arise in future years. I brought this to the attention of the Commission in my management letters on the 1999-2000 and 2000-01 financial statements. In 2002 the Commission's Internal Audit team undertook additional work to help determine the size and scope of the problem. The Commission is now developing a database with a view to producing the necessary information.
3. Where it is likely that payment will have to be made at a future date, in respect of a case funded by the Commission, Accounting Standards (FRS 12) require the Commission to disclose the extent of this liability in its accounts. Where a reliable estimate can be made the liability should be provided for in the accounts and where this is not possible the liability should be disclosed as a contingent liability in the notes to the accounts. The Commission has stated (note 16 to the accounts) that the outcome of the cases which it is funding is so uncertain that a provision for legal costs cannot safely be made. It has included a contingent liability of £3 million. My audit has confirmed that the Commission does not have sufficiently robust systems to substantiate this figure.
4. In my view it should be possible to make a reliable estimate for part of the future liability and, where this is not possible, a contingent liability should be included. The Commission has not made a provision for future liabilities and I have been unable to verify the figure included as a contingent liability. I have therefore qualified my opinion as the Commission has not complied with the accounting standard.

INCOME AND EXPENDITURE ACCOUNT FOR 12 MONTHS TO 31ST MARCH 2002

	Notes	12 months to 31/03/02 £	12 months to 31/03/01 £
INCOME			
Grant from the Office of the First and Deputy First Minister - Vote A Line 2	2	6,972,168	6,035,406
EXPENDITURE			
Staff Salaries and Commissioners' Fees	3	3,695,979	3,503,717
Operating Costs	4	1,618,429	1,249,285
Other Costs	5	1,682,981	1,470,310
Depreciation	1 & 6	140,433	132,903
Capital Expenditure Grant Release		(140,433)	(132,903)
		6,997,389	6,223,312
Notional Costs of Capital	10	3,438	3,073
TOTAL EXPENDITURE			
		7,000,827	6,226,385
Surplus (Deficit) for period		(28,659)	(190,979)
Credit in respect of Notional Costs	10	3,438	3,073
Transfer to Reserves		(25,221)	(187,906)

All amounts above relate to continuing activities.

The notes on pages 16 to 27 form part of these accounts.

Balance Sheet as at 31st March 2002

	Notes	12 months to 31/03/02 £	12 months to 31/03/01 £
Fixed Assets			
Tangible Assets	1 & 6	407,523	161,124
Current Assets			
Debtors	7	146,405	72,940
Cash & Bank	8 & 13	103,056	108,413
		249,461	181,353
Current Liabilities			
Amounts falling within 1 year	9	535,032	351,024
Net Current Liabilities		(285,571)	(169,671)
Total Assets less Current Liabilities		121,952	(8,547)
Creditors - amounts falling due after 1 year	11	38,820	48,128
Provisions	12	180,279	261,650
		(97,147)	(318,325)
Financed by			
Deferred government grants	13	407,523	160,393
General Fund	14	(504,670)	(479,449)
Revaluation Reserve	14	Nil	731
		(97,147)	(318,325)

The notes on pages 16 to 27 form part of these accounts.

Cash Flow Statement For 12 months to 31st March 2002

	Notes	12 months to 31/03/02 £	12 months to 31/03/01 £
Net cash inflow from operating activities	15	(5,357)	11,197
Capital Expenditure	6	(386,832)	(80,594)
Capital Grant Received		386,832	80,594
(Decrease)/Increase in Cash	2	(5,357)	11,197

The notes on pages 16 to 27 form part of these accounts

Statement of Total Recognised Gains and Losses For 12 months ended 31st March 2002

	Notes	12 months to 31/03/02 £	12 months to 31/03/01 £
Result for the period		(28,659)	(190,979)
Unrealized surplus/(deficit) on revaluation of fixed assets		Nil	Nil
Total recognised gains/(losses) for the period		(28,659)	(190,979)

The notes on pages 16 to 27 form part of these accounts.

The financial statements on pages 2 to 27 were approved by the Board of the Equality Commission on 13th November 2002 and were signed on its behalf by

Evelyn Collins
Chief Executive and Accounting Officer

Notes to the Accounts For the 12 months to 31st March 2002

1. ACCOUNTING POLICIES

1.1 Accounting Convention

The financial statements have been prepared in accordance with the historical cost convention and paragraph 7(2)(A) of Schedule 8 of the Northern Ireland Act 1998.

Without limiting the information given the financial statements comply with the accounting and disclosure requirements of the Companies (Northern Ireland) Order 1986, the accounting standards issued or adopted by the Accounting Standards Board and accounting and disclosure requirements issued by the Department of Finance and Personnel, insofar as those requirements are appropriate.

1.2 The activities of the Commission are fully funded by the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister. Income from other sources is immaterial. Permission must be sought from the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister before non-grant income can be applied to the Commission's activities. Non-grant income for which departmental approval to use is not forthcoming is surrendered to the Consolidated Fund.

Grants of a revenue nature are credited to the Income and Expenditure account in the year to which it relates. Grants appropriated for capital purposes are credited to a Deferred Income account and released to the Income and Expenditure account over the expected life of the assets.

1.3 All expenditure on goods and services fall within the ambit of the Grant in Aid and complies with the Commission's Financial Memorandum and government purchasing requirements.

1.4 Fixed Assets

(a) The fixed asset additions are fully funded by the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister.

(b) Tangible fixed assets have been valued on a mixture of historic cost and net current replacement costs.

(c) A capitalisation threshold of £500 is applied.

(d) Depreciation is provided on tangible assets at rates calculated to write off the cost of each asset evenly over its expected life as follows:

Furniture and Fittings	10 years
Office Equipment (heavy)	10 years
Office Equipment (light)	5 years
IT Equipment	3 years
Photocopiers	3 years

1.5 Pension Costs

Staff have the opportunity to join the Principal Civil Service Pension Scheme (NI). The expected cost of providing pensions, as calculated periodically by professionally qualified actuaries, is charged to the Income and Expenditure account so as to spread the cost over the service lives of employees in the Scheme, in such a way that the pension costs is a substantially level percentage of current and expected future pensionable payroll.

Superannuation contribution are funded as follows:

Salary Band -	£Nil	-	£14,799	12%
	£14,800	-	£30,299	13.5%
	£30,300	-	£65,699	17.5%
	£65,700	and over		19.5%

1.6 Value Added Tax

The Commission does not have any income which is subject to output VAT. Accordingly the Commission is not VAT registered and cannot recover any input tax.

1.7 Investments

The Commission does not undertake any investment activities.

1.8 Stocks

The value of stocks of consumables is immaterial and the Commission does not attribute a value for stocks in the accounts.

1.9 Legal Fees

It has been the policy of the Commission not to accrue for legal fees in respect of complainant support until they are known by way of invoices. The outcomes in processing cases are so varied and unpredictable that the Commission deemed it unsafe to otherwise accrue for legal commitments. However, a new management information system is currently being developed to enable a more accurate estimate of future potential liabilities to be made (see note on contingent liabilities).

2. Grant from the Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister

	Notes	12 months to 31/03/02 £	12 months to 31/03/01 £
Grant from Office of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister		7,359,000	6,116,000
Less transfer of capital element to deferred income	13	386,832	80,594
Revenue Grants credited to Income and Expenditure account		6,972,168	6,035,406

3. Salaries (including Commissioners)

	Notes	12 months to 31/03/02 £	12 months to 31/03/01 £
Commissioners' Fees	3(a)	164,696	162,636
Staff Salaries	3(b)	3,531,283	3,341,081
		3,695,979	3,503,717

3(a) Commissioners' Fees

Chief Commissioner's Fees		65,552	62,788
Social Security Costs		7,261	7,126
Pension Costs		11,471	12,244
		84,284	82,158
Other Commissioners' Fees		80,000	80,000
Social Security Costs		412	478
		164,696	162,636

3(b) Staff Costs

Directorate	Salary £	Social Security £	Pension Costs £	Agency Costs £	12 months to 31/03/02 £	12 months to 31/03/01 £
Disability	341,732	24,161	46,792	13,828	426,513	346,786
Fair Employment	1,171,481	82,148	166,341	105,600	1,525,570	1,491,070
Sex Equality	410,959	28,459	60,081	40,263	539,762	602,545
Race Equality	123,566	9,132	17,452	20,334	170,484	175,160
Statutory Duty	165,171	11,795	22,839	24,728	224,533	185,514
Resources	248,378	18,474	20,465	84,151	371,468	335,765
Executive	204,154	17,084	32,806	18,909	272,953	204,241
Total	2,665,441	191,253	366,776	307,813	3,531,283	3,341,081

The Chief Executive's salary does not include a performance-related bonus nor does she receive any taxable benefits in kind. The Chief Executive is a member of the Principal Civil Service Pension Scheme (NI) on the same basis as all other members of staff. At 31st March 2002 the Chief Executive has served 25 months of a 5 year service contract which may be renewed or made permanent subject to satisfactory performance. At the year-end she would have been entitled to compensation for premature loss of office amounting to the equivalent of 2.92 years' gross salary.

3(c) Average Number of Full Time Equivalentents

	12 months to 31/03/02 £	12 months to 31/03/01 £
Disability	22	14
Fair Employment	56	60
Sex Equality	19	26
Race Equality	8	7
Statutory Duty	10	7
Resources	18	15
Management	6	5
	139	134

3(d) Details are given below of salary and pension entitlement (excluding any pension benefits arising from Additional Voluntary Contributions or the pension benefits transferred from other schemes) of the Chief Commissioner, other Commissioners, the Chief Executive and Senior Management included in the above costs summaries.

	Age @ 31/03/02	Salary 12 mths to 31/03/02	Salary 6 mths to 31/03/02	Real increase in pension @ 60	Total Accrued Pension as at 31/03/02@
	£	£	£	£	£
<u>Commissioners</u>					
J Harbison (Chief Commissioner)	64	65,552	62,788	844	2,182
B Hinds (Deputy Chief Commissioner)		8,000	8,000	-	-
J Bryson		4,000	4,000	-	-
H Coll		4,000	4,000	-	-
R Connolly		4,000	4,000	-	-
P Donaghy		4,000	4,000	-	-
A Henry		4,000	4,000	-	-
J Heron		4,000	4,000	-	-
A Hope		4,000	4,000	-	-
R Lavery		4,000	4,000	-	-
S Livingstone		4,000	4,000	-	-
M Logue		4,000	4,000	-	-
H McConnell		4,000	4,000	-	-
S Malik		4,000	4,000	-	-
R Mullan		4,000	4,000	-	-
R Osborne		4,000	4,000	-	-
R Steele		4,000	4,000	-	-
A Man-Wah Lo		4,000	4,000	-	-
M Wilson		4,000	4,000	-	-
N Wright		4,000	4,000	-	-
		145,552	142,788		
<u>General Management</u>					
E Collins (Chief Executive)	43	54,810	52,500	917	13,604
B McNeany (Head of Operations and Corporate Services) Appointed 1/5/01	42	42,625		534	534
A McKeown (Head of Policy and Public Affairs) Appointed 1/7/01	36	33,750		422	422

“Salary” includes gross salary; performance pay or bonuses; overtime and any other allowance to the extent that it is subject to UK taxation.

Pension benefits are provided through the Principal Civil Service Pension Scheme (NI). This is a statutory scheme, which provides benefits on a “final salary” basis at a normal retirement age of 60. Benefits accrue at the rate of 1/80th of the pensionable salary for each year of service. In addition a lump sum equivalent to 3 years pension is payable on retirement. Members pay contribution of 1.5% of pensionable earnings. Pensions increase in payment in line with the Retail Price Index. On death, pensions are payable to the surviving spouse at a rate of half the member’s pension. On death in service the Scheme pays a lump sum benefit of twice pensionable pay and also provides a service enhancement on computing the spouse’s pension. The enhancement depends on length of service and cannot exceed 10 years. Medical retirement is possible in the event of serious ill health. In this case, pensions are brought into payment immediately without actuarial reduction and with service enhancement as for widow(er) pensions.

4. Operating Costs

	12 months to 31/03/02 £	12 months to 31/03/01 £
General Costs		
Travel & Subsistence	63,830	59,656
Staff Recruitment	35,339	90,264
Staff Training	51,068	58,822
Postage	38,116	50,676
Telephones	48,535	47,745
Hospitality	1,638	2,972
Audit	7,275	16,440
Insurance	10,242	11,351
Miscellaneous	30,673	39,406
Office Consumables	78,959	104,338
R&M Office Equipment	13,938	4,185
Annual Contracts	82,803	28,024
Library	797	31,935
Legal Costs	81,050	4,667
Corporate Services	42,562	11,463
	586,825	561,944
Premises Costs		
Rents	710,624	299,923
Rates	41,673	81,043
Service Charge	72,490	74,203
Electricity/ Gas	44,193	29,422
R&M Buildings	28,476	32,656
Refurbishment/ Relocation	85,545	54,115
High Court action/commercial dispute	8,710	93,000
Cleaning	39,893	22,979
	1,031,604	687,341
	1,618,429	1,249,285

5. Other Costs

	12 months to 31/03/02 £					12 months to 31/03/01 £	
Commission Expenses						29,712	36,334
	Disability £	Race £	Gender £	Religion £	Stat. D £		
Education & Advice	97,027	133,507	66,119	85,484	94,485	476,622	492,778
Legal Fees	88,333	156,106	631,861	170,261	-	1,046,561	653,890
Investigations Research & Consultancy	31,848	24,529	44,520	13,660	15,529	130,086	287,308
	217,208	314,142	742,500	269,405	110,014		
						1,682,981	1,470,310

6. Fixed Assets

	Information Technology £	Office Equipment £	Furniture £	Fixtures £	Total £
Valuation as at 31/03/01	298,717	149,446	177,287	Nil	625,450
Additions	66,619	49,937	230,842	39,434	386,832
Disposals	29,082	45,932	153,232	Nil	228,246
Valuation as at 31/03/02	336,254	153,451	254,897	39,434	784,036
Accum. Depreciation as at 31/03/01	171,740	130,603	161,983	Nil	464,326
Depreciation for the period	95,268	16,333	24,889	3,943	140,433
Depreciation on Disposals	29,082	45,932	153,232	Nil	228,246
Accum. Depreciation as at 31/03/02	237,926	101,004	33,640	3,943	376,513
Net Book Value as at 31/03/02	98,328	52,447	221,257	35,491	407,523
Net Book Value as at 31/03/01	126,977	18,843	15,304	Nil	161,124

The office equipment includes capitalised leased equipment with a net book value of £Nil. The depreciation charge in respect of this equipment for the year was £Nil. Peppercorn rentals have been charged directly to revenue.

7. Debtors: amounts due within 12 months

	31/03/02	31/03/01
	£	£
Prepayments	146,405	65,421
Debtors	Nil	7,519
	<hr/> 146,405	<hr/> 72,940

8. Cash at Bank and in Hand

	31/03/02	31/03/01
	£	£
Cash in Bank	103,030	108,304
Cash in Hand	26	109
	<hr/> 103,056	<hr/> 108,413

9. Creditors and Accruals: amounts falling due within 12 months

	31/03/02	31/03/01
	£	£
Sundry Creditors and Accruals	523,951	336,270
Early Retirement Costs	11,081	14,754
	<hr/> 535,032	<hr/> 351,024

10. Notional Costs

The Income and Expenditure account bears a non-cash charge for interest relating to the use of capital. The basis of the charge is 6% per annum on the average capital employed defined as the average of total assets less current liabilities.

11. Creditors: amounts falling due after 1 year

	31/03/02	31/03/01
	£	£
Early Retirement Costs	38,820	48,128

12. Provisions

	31/03/02	31/03/01
	£	£
Legal Fees (cases lodged against former bodies and the Commission)	45,000	18,650
Premises	126,000	150,000
Other	9,279	Nil
High Court Action - Commercial Dispute	Nil	93,000
	<hr/> 180,279	<hr/> 261,650

13. Deferred Income

Capital Allocations not yet released to Income and Expenditure Account

	31/03/02	31/03/01
	£	£
As at 31/03/01	160,393	212,702
Received in period	386,832	80,594
Released to Income and Expenditure	(140,433)	(132,903)
Revaluation Reserve	731	-
	407,523	160,393

14. Reconciliation of Movements in Reserve Funds

	General Reserve £	Revaluation Reserve £	31/03/01 £	31/03/01 £
At 1st April 2001	(479,449)	731	(291,543)	731
Transfer from Income and Expenditure Account	(28659)	Nil	(190,979)	Nil
Credit in respect of notional cost of capital	3,438	Nil	3,073	Nil
Surplus and Revaluation of Fixed Assets	Nil	(731)	Nil	Nil
	(504,670)	Nil	(479,449)	731

15. Notes to Cash Flow Statement

15.1 Reconciliation of result for period to net cash inflow from operating statement

	31/03/02	31/03/01
	£	£
Result for the period	(28,659)	(190,979)
Adjustment for non-cash transactions:		
Credit for notional charge	3,438	3,073
Depreciation	140,433	132,903
Amounts written off assets	Nil	Nil
Capital grant release	(140,433)	(132,903)
Adjustments for movements in working capital:		
Decrease/(increase) in debtors	(73,465)	(27,463)
Increase/(decrease) in provisions	(81,371)	93,000
(Decrease)/increase in creditors	184,008	105,884
(Decrease)/increase in creditors - over 1 year	(9,308)	27,682
Net cash flow	<u>(5,357)</u>	<u>11,197</u>

15.2 Reconciliation of net cash inflow to movement in net funds

	31/03/02	31/03/01
	£	£
Opening Cash	108,413	97,216
Net Cash inflow	(5,357)	11,197
Closing Cash	<u>103,056</u>	<u>108,413</u>

16. Contingent Liabilities

A number of cases have been taken against the Equality Commission and the three former bodies on employment practices.

It is the Commission's intention to defend rigorously these claims and a provision of £45,000 has been made in respect of costs for these claims.

Having obtained legal advice and on the basis of the information available, the Commission believes that the provision made represents the best estimate of the outcomes of the various claims and their associated costs.

One of the key strategic objectives of the Commission is to combat discrimination and to promote equality of opportunity. In working towards this objective, the Commission offers support to complainants in cases of alleged discrimination. The extent, procedures and outcomes of this assistance is so uncertain that provision for the future commitment of legal fees can not safely be made.

The Commission is currently supporting more than 1,100 cases with potential legal fees liability in excess of £3,000,000 anticipated over the next three years. New procedures are being implemented which should reduce this potential liability.

17. Related Party Transactions

The Equality Commission is a non-departmental public body sponsored by the Office of the First and Deputy First Minister (OFMDFM). OFMDFM is regarded as a related party. During the year the Commission has various material transactions with OFMDFM and various other bodies for which OFMDFM is regarded as the parent body.

There have been various at-arms-length transactions between the Commission and certain Commissioners detailed as follows:

Rosemary Connolly, a practicing solicitor was paid £46,734 in fees relating to complainant support. This figure includes £25,057 of outlay.

Monica Wilson is the Chief Executive of Disability Action. During the year Disability Action received £14,734 in respect of consultancy and grants.

Anna Man-Wah Lo is the Director of the Chinese Welfare Association. £164 was paid to the Chinese Welfare Association in respect of translation services throughout the year.

Ruth Lavery is a Member of the Carers National Association to which a grant of £500 was awarded.

Harry Coll is a practicing solicitor with Elliott Duffy Garrett Solicitors who were paid £51,691. This figure includes £42,311 in costs awarded against the Commission in the commercial dispute with its ex-landlord.

Can we help you?

We are here to help you. If you need help or advice or would like to find out more about the Equality Commission and its work, contact us at:

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Equality Commission

FOR NORTHERN IRELAND

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